

D3.1 Ontology with well- defined taxonomy and metadata for the targeted databases agreed and reported

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDE	Common Data Environment
DC	Data Cellar
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DoA	Description of Action
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Digital Twin
EC	Energy Community
ESCO	Energy Service Company
GA	Grant Agreement
HMI	Human Machine Interface
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO OBP	International Organization for Standardization’s Online Browsing Platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEC	Local Energy Community
LOT	Linked Open Terms
ML	Machine Learning
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
UC	Use Case
VC	Validation Case
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D3.1 “Ontology with well-defined taxonomy and metadata for the targeted databases agreed and reported” in the framework of the Project titled “Data hub for the Creation of Energy communities at Local Level and to Advance Research on them” (Project Acronym: DATA CELLAR; Grant Agreement No.: 101069694).

This document has been prepared to provide a detailed description of the activities within Task 3.1 (T3.1), entitled “Assessment of relevant existing EU databases and how to interconnect to them and the other ENERGY Dataspace”, on the scope of Work Package 3 (WP3), entitled “Interoperability and Federation of EU Energy Data Spaces”.

In this deliverable, the “Ontology with well-defined taxonomy and metadata for the targeted databases agreed and reported” is detailed with exhaustive reference to the status in Ontology practices with specific emphasis to the disciplines of energy.

Particular emphasis has been given to the existing or currently running practices in the field, by providing an in-depth exploration of the prevailing EU databases within the specific context of data and information that exhibit significant pertinence to the validation cases of DATA CELLAR. Knowing that the current objective of DATA CELLAR is to construct an ontology specifically tailored to the energy domain serving the energy communities, the current report provides a comprehensive account of the procedural stages involved in implementing the LOT methodology for the development of the energy domain ontology.

For this purpose, the aim through the work within T3.1 reported in this deliverable, is to leverage relevant databases, such as energy, environment-related repositories, and respective linked data. These sources of information not only inform the ontology development process but also stimulate it by providing valuable insights and up-to-date knowledge about these domains. One of the key benefits of using relevant databases is presented as the access to energy and environment-related repositories. These repositories are dedicated to collecting and organizing data pertaining to energy and/or environmental data. They can act as valuable resources for the DATA CELLAR ontology developers, since they provide a wealth of information about the entities, attributes, and relationships that exist within these domains. This, linked data, plays a significant role in supporting ontology development. Linked data makes use of a method of publishing and connecting structured data in digital forms (i.e., online databases, dedicated servers, etc.), following standardized formats and using semantic technologies.

In the paragraphs above, specific emphasis is given to understand the role and purpose of ontologies and how these can form the basis of traceability and interoperability. Ontologies can be used in *databases* and *dataspaces* to provide a semantic framework for organizing and linking data and information. By incorporating an ontology into a dataspace, the relationships between data elements can be made explicit and can be used to enhance data search, retrieval, and integration. The proposed methodology concerning ontology development to be applied for the DATA CELLAR energy domain is presented in detail under Section 0. As concluded through a detailed presentation of current practices in Section 0, the DATA CELLAR methodology is based primarily on the **Linked**

Open Terms (LOT)¹ methodology, and partially on the **METHONTOLOGY**². The fundamental process steps of both methodologies are principally complementary, including the activities of **(i) Specification (ii) Implementation and Conceptualization (iii) Maintenance and (iv) Evaluation**. Analysing these additions, it is noted **that some parts of the methodology have been adapted, or specialized for the DATA CELLAR needs and are documented in the corresponding sections**.

In Section 4 the following attributes of the process are detailed since they play a crucial role in the development of a dependable ontology of the planned DATA CELLAR data space:

- **Taxonomies** that play a vital role in **conceptual modelling** and have gained even greater significance with the advent of the extended Entity-Relationship model.
- **Metadata** that by definition refers to **data that provides information about other data**. Thus, metadata is “**data about data**” and can include a wide variety of information, such as format, size, location, date, etc. Metadata address the *who, what, when, where, and why* of these data.
- **Data and metadata Schemas** that are the **core of any database**, which serves as the foundation for organizing, storing, and accessing data. A data schema is essentially a blueprint or structure that outlines how data is stored and processed within a database.
- **Knowledge Graphs** that are a **representation and reasoning**, drawing inspiration from human problem-solving approaches, that aim to encode knowledge to empower intelligent systems in solving complex tasks.

In Section 5 the DATA CELLAR Ontology Development Methodology is presented giving the evidence for the choices made in adapting the LOT principles, while METHONTOLOGY elements are exploited to enhance the development process where relevant. Through this approach, the intention is to create the DATA CELLAR ontology by constructing a network of ontologies or modules that are interconnected through shared concepts and relationships. Each domain is constructed according to the process depicted in Section 5 and more specifically Figure 3, which identifies the actors/users participating in each step, the activities, and the resulting outputs based on the schema indicated by LOT.

Section 6 analyses the importance of ontologies Reuse in DATA CELLAR. Stressing that developing Local Energy Communities (LEC) is a multidisciplinary research activity since engineering, economics, and meteorology experts often work together. For this reason, a common vocabulary that described the players (human beings and devices) and their possible interactions is mandatory to properly interact. Moreover, if well-designed, already existing ontologies can be reused, increasing the integration and interoperability of different systems. For this reason, care is taken in this section to briefly describe the existing ontologies that have been reused to implement the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology, under the LOT - implementation step. Five such existing ontologies have been presented with details to validate the importance of using them.

¹ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

² Gomez-Perez, Asuncion & Fernández-López, Mariano & Corcho, Oscar. (2004). *Ontological Engineering: With Examples from the Areas of Knowledge Management, E-Commerce and the Semantic Web*.

Section 7 the methodology for data Migration between Ontologies is presented to ascertain the pursued interoperability principles that can be adapted from and to the DATA CELLAR ontology. Hence the procedure for converting data in different formats into an RDF graph that adheres to the DATA CELLAR ontology is analysed. As indicated, this conversion is crucial to unify diverse data assets and add semantic annotations, enabling their effective utilization within the DATA CELLAR ecosystem. As it is underlined, although the existing data assets hold significant value, their usefulness is limited without an interoperable model like the DATA CELLAR ontology to connect them.

Section 8 addresses the issues related to DATA CELLAR Ontology Conceptualization as an input to the PROTEGE encoding that is used as the adapted method within DATA CELLAR. The importance in implementing this step is the fact that domain-specific ontologies serve as means to define the ontological agreements and commitments between information providers and users within an information infrastructure. They leverage domain-specific knowledge to address the challenges posed by the overwhelming amount of information available. As clarified, this is accomplished through two key approaches: (i) Reusing and organizing knowledge from existing real-world ontologies: This involves mapping semantic concepts from ontologies to data structures in underlying repositories. By doing so, knowledge can be efficiently reused and organized, enabling effective information management. (ii) Integrating and developing mechanisms for translating information requests across ontologies: This entails creating methods and tools to bridge the gap between different ontologies and facilitate the exchange of information. By enabling seamless communication across ontologies, the integration and translation of knowledge becomes possible, improving the overall interoperability and effectiveness of information retrieval processes.

Exploring this need, the report tabulates the attributes of the selected ontological categories addressed by the DATA CELLAR which are:

- Energy market structures and pricing;
- Energy regulations, policies, and standards;
- Energy efficiency technologies;
- Energy generation technologies and sources;
- Energy transmission and distribution systems;
- Energy consumption and usage patterns;
- Energy storage systems and technologies;
- Smart Devices.

In Section 9 details are presented of the capabilities of the PROTEGE framework selected for the DATA CELLAR Ontology. PROTÉGÉ, a renowned ontology editor and framework, being a powerful open-source tool developed by the esteemed Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research. With its adaptable plug-and-play environment, it enables users to create knowledge-driven solutions, providing a versatile foundation for rapid prototyping. This report gives evidence of the robust desktop application of PROTÉGÉ, which empowers the DATA CELLAR ontology developers to generate RDF files, seamlessly migrate data using multiple methods, and achieve visual optimizations of the ontologies. Visual solutions are presented depicting them in Knowledge Graphs and OntoGraf / RDF Graphs for the selected ontological categories.

As can be appreciated, the solutions presented in this report are not publicly available and further steps are expected as work progresses in the next phases of the project and these are indicated below:

- The ontology is to be made publicly available in publicly accessible platforms (such as zenodo) in the future during the project.
- Some of the evaluation steps are not fully addressed since the ontology is only available in the boundaries of SharePoint.
- The relevant hosting URIs cannot be published due to the premature status of the ontology as currently developed.
- **The evaluation stage under D3.1 involves an initial assessment since the ontology is not published online before the deliverable's finalization. The online publication requires the completion of data model and a more finalized status of interoperability.**

2. Introduction

2.1. Project Summary

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as a pivotal measure to play a key role in driving the EU's energy transition. At the same time, the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors appear crucial to foster the exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society's most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models to serve and support the spread of energy communities in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized data space to store streams or historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The data space will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, energy communities, private businesses, and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs.

To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 WPs with different objectives, tasks and deliverables.

WP3 plays the important role of liaison with the other data space initiatives as well as with other relevant EU and non-EU Energy data spaces. For achieving this degree of cooperation and

interoperability it is vitally important to have a well-defined ontology of the targeted data. Common definitions, architectures of systems, taxonomies of active components and systems (e.g., technologies, sub-technologies, functionalities), along with metadata terms, are required to build an effective repository facilitating searchability, built on open standards towards a linked common environment, offering collectively improved features and enriched data, information, and knowledge.

2.2. Deliverable objectives and overview

Task 3.1 aims to identify other existing EU databases and/or dataspace, and their primary goals. Furthermore, this undertaking aims to cultivate a comprehensive ontology for the energy sector, with the overarching objective of ensuring consistent utilization of taxonomy and metadata. By safeguarding the ignition of the DATA CELLAR, this initiative actively addresses the specific intricacies of the energy domain, serving as a foundational pillar for achieving targeted interoperability.

Deliverable D3.1 provides the main results of T3.1. It is organized into 10 Chapters:

- *Chapter 1* is an executive summary, which provides the content of the deliverable in a nutshell.
- *Chapter 2* is the introduction, where the structure of the deliverable and its objectives are declared.
- *Chapter 3* assesses relevant existing EU databases, pointing out their goals and their influence towards ontology development for the energy domain.
- *Chapter 4* presents the proposed methodology concerning ontology development to be applied within DATA CELLAR and its interaction with the Section 0 databases/dataspace.
- *Chapter 5* describes step by step the processes for developing the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology.
- *Chapter 6* provides an assessment of other existing ontologies that have been reused to develop DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology.
- *Chapter 7* provides technical details related to the ontology development process, and in particular on migrating data to ontologies via various paths.
- *Chapter 8* demonstrates the conceptual documentation of the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology.
- *Chapter 9* provides the main schemas of the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology, developed through the PROTÉGÉ framework.
- *Chapter 10* points out the main results of T3.1 and suggests future directions.

2.3. Relation to other tasks and deliverables

The interactions and dependencies of T3.1 to other tasks are illustrated in Figure 2.

T1.1 wants to identify user needs and expectations starting from feedback received from the VCs. The interactions between T1.1 and T3.1 have allowed to identify data to populate DATA CELLAR in line with the databases/dataspace considered for the energy domain specific.

Similarly, T2.1 wants to identify and classify data that will be collected. This information was considered as input for T3.1.

Moreover, T3.1 provides information to T3.2 and T7.2:

- T3.2 aims to define the principles of connectivity and portability to be used in DATA CELLAR. In this context, the output of T3.1 will provide suggestions to T3.2 to make DATA CELLAR interoperable and compatible with other dataspace.
- T4.1 aims to the development of the DATA CELLAR data model, thus T3.1 provides a robust and well-structured taxonomy regarding the energy specific domain T3.1 can constitute the base for developing the data model.
- T7.2 wants to create Energy Scenarios via DATA CELLAR to study the impact of energy communities in the EU energy system. To implement them, the data identified by T3.1 will be considered.

Figure 2 - Interactions and dependencies of Task 3.1

3. Targeted EU Databases

During the activities of T1.1 – “Users and Market Needs Characterization via a participatory approach”, the Validation Cases’ representatives and potential DATA CELLAR users were inquired on their wishes and needs regarding the DATA CELLAR dataspace and its functionalities. An online questionnaire was distributed to identified stakeholders, with different backgrounds and relation with the Consortium, to identify their literacy on data spaces, and their wishes and needs, for a proper development of the project’s activities (see DATA CELLAR D1.1 – “DATA CELLAR potential users’ wishes and needs collected via a participatory approach also for LEC self-assessment tool development³” for the complete set of questions and answers). Also, a workshop with Validation Cases’ representatives was organized to discuss these wishes and needs. For the development of the workshop, research was conducted on current data spaces at national, regional, and European level, to collect information regarding their functions and operations.

It was identified that a similar activity had to be made on the scope of T3.1. Therefore, a collaboration was agreed between both task leaders (EDP, representing T1.1) and UBE (representing T3.1). The identification of data space and databases started in T1.1 and finished in T3.1, each one focusing on what was important at every step. The databases described in the following section represents the result of this joint effort in terms of identification and relevant information.

3.1. EU Databases’ Goals and Relevant for DATA CELLAR Information

The initial establishment of the database inventory took place in an online format, specifically utilizing the .xlsx file format, which resides within the SharePoint platform dedicated to the project. This configuration ensures seamless accessibility for all project partners involved. The online document comprises meticulously curated and evaluated information concerning databases that are deemed and agreed as relevant to the DATA CELLAR.

This section presents a comprehensive analysis that encompasses the primary objectives of the listed databases and dataspace. Furthermore, it incorporates pertinent information that establishes correlations with the DATA CELLAR, particularly in the context of validation cases (and considering the sub-task 2.1.1 – “Focus on validation VCs”). The information of each database/dataspace included are categorised as: (i) primary goals, (ii) weather data in different EU locations, (iii) smart meter energy data, (iv) thermal/cooling consumption, (v) electricity consumption, (vi) grid need for flexibility data, (vii) specific load controls, (viii) wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations, (ix) power production rates of different assets, (x) energy costs, (xi) other data relevant to DATA CELLAR. Each category's description is provided based on the availability within the respective projects. Categories that have not been populated are marked as "non-applicable."

1. COORDINATE⁴

Primary goals: To use the database (i) to check for network violations, (ii) to manage the network congestions and (iii) check for technical violations on the

³ <https://datacellarproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/D1.1-DATA-CELLAR-potential-users-wishes-and-needs-collected-via-a-participatory-approach-also-for-LEC-self-assessment-too.pdf>

⁴ <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/>

network. The data is used as a baseline to run simulation on data-driven models, also known as “black boxes”. The data are also be exchanged between the project’s other tools, actors, and between the market platform tools.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Smart meter energy data:** It is owned by the DSOs of the countries involved on the project. The Spanish dataset is not openly available due to the link between sensitive data and confidential metering data; the Swedish dataset is also not openly available, but historic and real-time are available via secure transfer; the Greek data must be acquired directly from the smart meters, and written permission must be provided by the owner and/or responsible for the data.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** non-applicable.
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** acquired via smart meter data, as described.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** (i) Spain: To determine the needs of the Distribution System Operator (DSO) for congestion management, it is essential to provide sufficient and comprehensive data about the electrical network. The data is in ".csv" format and amounts to approximately 2 GB. It is generated through forecasting and optimal power flow models, as well as topology simplifying models, which are not publicly accessible. However, a set of anonymized data can be made available for dissemination purposes. In terms of flexibility services providers, the aggregation platform can utilize real-time measurements, historical data, and status information from flexible assets. This data is utilized to create flexibility bids and operate flexible assets based on the market clearing results. The data includes technical specifications of the end devices providing flexibility, as well as technical data from SCADA systems, sensors, and meters used in the production process for electrical energy control. This encompasses electrical data and various other types of measured data. (ii) Sweden: Offers the capability to identify various aspects such as capabilities, performance, capacity cost, availability, and endurance. It enables forecasting, running demos, and conducting analyses. However, this information is not openly accessible, except for assets larger than 100 MW. The details concerning Flexibility Service Providers (FSB) will not be disseminated. (iii) Greece: Flexibility requirements will be transmitted to the market platform to commence the market procedure. The data can be provided in either ".json" or ".csv" format. It may contain information regarding the price per Megawatt or Megawatt-hour. The flexibility needs are calculated by performing an optimal power flow analysis that considers load and renewable energy source (RES) forecasting. The data is stored in private cloud storage, accessible with proper permission obtained through written consent from the data owner or responsible party.
- **Specific load control:** In the context of the Spanish case, the data encompasses information from sensors and meters employed in the production process to monitor and regulate electrical energy, which includes electrical data. This data is derived from sensors and device controllers situated at the facilities that offer flexibility. However, no specific information is available regarding other cases.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** (i) Spain: there is available data of the network status. It is conducted an evaluation of the participation in any service (MW), an assessment of the total energy, in MWh, provided to different services. There is under 2GB of data, only accessible to one party, for the sole purpose of market clearing, development of future forecasting and optimal power flows tools. For the market participation to know the market results, statistics on efficiency of the market; this set of data cannot be used for dissemination because it is linked to sensitive and confidential metering data ownership of the DSO/RES

owners. (ii) Greece: renewable energy sources and distributed generation data will be used to detect potential congestions or voltage violations and calculate the required flexibility. There is wind and PV forecasting available, acquired from AMR system in distribution system, acquired from SCADA system and sent to EMS system in transmission system, and available since ask for written permission from the owner/responsible for the data.

- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** (i) Spain: there is a provision of sufficient data of the electrical network to determine DSO needs for congestions management. To perform power flows, it is determined the flexibility needs, it's detected congestions and capacity of relevant lines. There is also data generated from optimal power flows models and topology. The total amount of data is under 2GB, only accessible to one party, for the sole purpose of market clearing. The data set cannot be used for dissemination because it is linked to sensitive and confidential network and substation data in ownership of the DSO. (ii) Sweden: the related data is used to prepare and develop structures to ensure proper market configuration and integration, to do forecasting and run demos; market structure and grid schematics. The amount of data is under 1 GB, is considered sensitive information: Therefore, only an overview can be delivered.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** non-applicable.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

2. INTERCONNECT⁵

Primary goals: (i) To define the interconnection between different digital platforms and aligning existing standards towards allowing different stakeholders to focus on the development of innovative services for human-centric energy ecosystem; (ii) the implementation of a digital marketplace composed by different platforms and showcase the satisfaction of energy users with cost-effective solutions, allowing different market agents to create their value, and simultaneously ensure high levels of cybersecurity and data privacy; (iii) the co-creation involving citizens to design energy, and non-energy services and applications that foster the active participation in new business models and grid operation, while ensuring comfortable, efficient, sustainable and healthier living environments.

interconnect

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** The project aims to use weather forecasts to predict energy supply and demand, but do not mention how to acquire this data.
- **Smart meter energy data:** one of the partners of the consortium formed to develop this project is specialized in smart metering solutions. Part of the buildings of the pilot already have smart meter, from previous projects. Some partners have budget to install smart meter on the pilots.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** there is some data available of thermal consumption of heat pumps. Otherwise, some of non-residential buildings consume heat, but there are no insights on its measurement.
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** data from smart meters and the provision of smart meters for electricity measurement.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** by the exploitation of flexibility potential of smart appliances, storage and electric vehicles, the interoperable platforms to be developed must inform the flexibility-related data to the grid operators.
- **Specific load control:** all pilots that already have HEMS, PV inverters and smart appliances.

⁵ <https://interconnectproject.eu/>

- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** the maximization of usage of renewable energy sources in energy communities aims to enable the activation of user flexibility to match the production of a local wind turbine and solar park. Furthermore, some residential pilots already have PV systems installed, and the project budget mention the installation of a series of local PV systems.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** based on the data acquired from the smart meters of different energy carriers the ratio of each asset can be calculated. No prior information on this matter.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** one of the main objectives of the project is to optimize every energy consumption costs. Therefore, the baseline with actual costs must be acquired to compare.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

3. OMEGA-X⁶

Primary goals: The aim of OMEGA-X is to implement a Data Space (based on European common standards), including federated infrastructure, data marketplace and service marketplace, involving data sharing between different stakeholders and demonstrating its value for real and concrete Energy use cases and needs, while guaranteeing scalability and interoperability with other Data Spaces initiatives, not just for energy but also cross-sector.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Renewable energy use case family:** more than 2 years of historical data, from 7 different sources, with 10-min resolution.
- **Local energy communities use case family:** approximately 1 GB per year, comprising ambient temperature, solar irradiation, wind speed, with 15-min resolution. Other source also has approximately 1 GB of undisclosed data, with 1-s resolution (considered real-time).
- **Smart meter energy data:** regarding the LEC use cases family, there is approximately 30 GB per year of natural gas, electricity, and district heating/cooling flow meters. Also, there is information on a meter level of water consumption, along with district heating and electricity, from another source.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** (i) Boiler / heat pump: approximately 10GB per year of operational parameter, with 15-min resolution, or even less. (ii) District heating: approximately 15GB per year of thermal energy produced and gas consumed by combined heat and power units, with 10-s resolution. (iii) Local thermal plant: 6 years of data, with 10GB of size, acquired from a SCADA with 15 data points, each second.
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** all originated from smart meters, also with EV charging, usage of BESS, and total amount of electricity consumed acquired via energy bills.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** to leverage data from multiple actors (DSO, Aggregators, Prosumers, etc.) to develop digital twins and data driven services both for real-time application and future planning applications to offer enhanced flexibility services. For instance, a digital twin reproducing the real behaviour of the Low Voltage grid will be automatically built from data shared by smart meters from E-Redes, from data shared by PV producers, EV charging stations and

⁶ <https://omega-x.eu/>

flexible loads. There is available data from characteristics of EVs, their availability for charging and consumption, energy exported to the grid and a set of consumer related data.

- **Specific load control:** provide grid services through frequency and voltage control by the LEC members via aggregation.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** there is no wind turbines involved on the project. Regarding PV, there is operational data from 175 plants over the area of operation of one of the partners. There is 15 GB per year of data related to the production of the LEC members. Also, operational data from installed PV plants in France. Lastly, there is 4.2 GB per year of data from PVs on buildings totalizing 40 kW.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** there is mostly PV involved on the project, with plenty of data regarding their production. Also, there is some data from CHP units and hydro plants.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** must be acquired from the project pilots.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** Grid (DSO and TSO) data: demand, flexibility needs, tariffs, georeferenced data, ERP infrastructure (e.g., accounting, procurement, project management, risk management, compliance, supply chain operations), inside building environmental data/ambient monitoring, Building Management System as a whole, fire safety-related data, resources (watering water, swimming pool usage etc.) schedule data.

4. IDSA⁷

Primary goals: (i) To promote secure and sovereign data exchange, certification and governance for business and industry across Europe and around the world, while comprising relationships between trusted partners

INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES ASSOCIATION

that are governed by the IDSA standard. (ii) To promote applications in the fields of AI, IoT, or big data; projects such as GAIA-X or AI4EU – all these application areas and endeavours are inconceivable without IDS. (iii) To promote open standards for facilitating secure and trusted data sharing to connect various platforms in an accepted and standardized manner that is guided by the principles of data sovereignty. IDS should be integrated as an inherent component in future architecture models of the data economy. (iv) IDS leverage the full value adding potential of data, data must be describable and tradeable with the help of a global, interoperable standard which has not been in place so far. (v) Forecast of local air quality based on dynamic traffic data & Incorporation of the forecast into traffic control (by ZE group).

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** weather data are exploited by IDS for integration in architecture of traffic scenarios, industry domain and wind farms.
- **Smart meter energy data:** The overall goal is to facilitate data sharing and exchange that is scalable, secure, and grants data sovereignty to data owners and providers. Digital business models established with the help of data spaces allow each party involved in a data sharing and exchange transaction to leverage the full value of their data. The concept is already working for smart grids, in which smart meters capture and communicate data on the energy consumed by individual households.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** IDSA provides a scientific and comprehensive framework for leveraging thermal/cooling consumption data in industrial settings. It enables secure data sharing, fosters collaboration among stakeholders, and empowers

⁷ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

informed decision-making to optimize energy efficiency and drive sustainable practices in thermal and cooling management.

- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** non-applicable.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** non-applicable.
- **Specific load control:** non-applicable.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** Most European wind turbine component suppliers, engineering companies or ICT companies cannot obtain, manage, analyse, and learn from the data produced by wind turbines in operation, thus missing the opportunity to improve their competitiveness. The use case shows how the adoption of the IDS Reference Architecture boosts the exchange of the data monitored by the sensors installed in wind turbines, which belong to the wind farm owner and the OEM, with other interested third parties such as technology and component suppliers, as secure data exchange and data sovereignty is guaranteed. Furthermore, it is also shown how this data sharing enables added value creation through information fusion. The deployment of the solution combines edge processing with the cloud demonstrating its applicability in wind turbine plants.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** The Mobility Data Space (MDS), an open IDS-based data space that goes beyond the secure exchange of sensitive mobility data, as well as linking existing data platforms with one another (cf. Mobility Data Marketplace – MDM). In this way, comprehensive mobility data can be made available in the future without fear of misuse of the data.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** non-applicable.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

5. GAIA-X⁸

Primary goals: (i) Brings together industry, politics, government, research, academic, technical, and scientific leaders from Europe and beyond to collaborate on the next generation of trusted data infrastructures; creating an open, transparent, and secure digital ecosystem, where data and services can

be made available, collated and shared in an environment of trust. (ii) To create a modern data infrastructure for the EU, its states, its companies, its citizens, and its global partners. (iii) To imply an infrastructure as the cradle of an ecosystem, where data and services can be made available, collected, and shared in an environment of trust. (iv) To focus on the precise needs of users and the added benefit as presented by the use cases. (v) To contribute horizontally to the added values of data availability, innovation, data sovereignty.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** In confines of farming domain, GAIA-X sets the foundations for communicating data across different platforms and IoT devices such as infield sensors with the agricultural software solution of choice, since monitoring field properties from different data platforms is a solution for real-time infield data analysis including weather data, topography of fields, crop vegetation indices and soil conditions; enable the efficient operation of energy communities, a wide variety of data from different actors must be combined. These data also include weather data to predict at what time additional electricity will have to be supplied from outside due to insufficient light incidence; different actors, including municipalities, weather services or tourism associations, are networked in the Data Space and possess different data.

⁸ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

- **Smart meter energy data:** GAIA-X Smart Living Shared Data Space aims to enabling cross-domain smart devices and applications. A smart home, a smart building or a group of smart buildings can interact with some degree of intelligence with smart energy networks, smart city structures, smart mobility offerings and smart assistance services., while the Information gained from smart buildings are useful and even essential for all these domains. GAIA-X creates a secure cloud with protected access for actors (residents, owners, energy service providers, and contractors) to the usage data needed for energy forecasting, e.g., energy consumption and behaviour-specific information such as arrival and departure times and any absences. GAIA-X enables a uniform and holistic pool of information to be established on all relevant devices installed in a building. GAIA-X gathers large amounts of heterogeneous data to address valuable use cases. Regarding smart metering it is conducted by Energy consumers, as households, local collective clusters, industrials (smart metering data).
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** Energy production plant data (e.g., pump status, temperature levels) and measured values (e.g., electricity and heat quantities) can be securely transferred from the quarter's production plants to a GAIA-X-based cloud infrastructure. GAIA-X involves data-based solutions to network the relevant energy consumers, producers, and storage systems across different buildings. In addition to the devices that are already widely connected today – such as heating and cooling installations and all types of IoT and household appliances – an important role will also be played by power-to-heat (PtH).
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** data via smart meters.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** GAIA-X is planned as an open and flexible data infrastructure. Therefore, cloud providers who have not been involved in the project so far can participate at any time if they clearly share the values and ambitions of GAIA-X - data sovereignty and data availability - and fulfil the common rules for participation. The balance of interests is to be ensured on the one hand by organising the entity as a neutral instance. In addition, the GAIA-X guidelines, principles, and standards also formulate corresponding objectives for maintaining neutrality, openness, transparency, and data sovereignty.
- **Specific load control:** non-applicable.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** GAIA-X Energy Data Space asset provides data management and valorisation on a change in paradigm which needs to consider specificities of the data and the complexities of the life-cycle management: (i) different technologies offered by equipment manufacturers: Vestas, Siemens, etc., (ii) diversity of contracts with equipment manufacturers, data providers, (iii) strong commitment to third parties on the performance rate of turbines, (iv) large volume of data, inconsistency making it impossible to share the results and use them (interoperability), (v) difficulties accessing data from some farms.
- Via GAIA-X, large amounts of heterogeneous data can be gathered to address the most valuable use cases, including Energy providers: for the production and storage of energy for all the different kinds of decarbonized energies, energy efficiency and new services. GAIA-X enables the networking of more than 50,000 energy production plants distributed across Germany to create a green-powered digital infrastructure (solar parks, wind farms, biogas plants, hydroelectric power plants).
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** Via GAIA-X, large amounts of heterogeneous data can be gathered to address the most valuable use cases, including Energy providers: for the production and storage of energy for all the different kinds of decarbonized energies, energy efficiency and new services. To get more accurate response of the flexibility portfolio at local level (e.g., heat pump, electric car...),

the incentivization could be based on artificial model calculating best dynamic tariff price based on previous reaction.

- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** Positive effects of open data result from the use of data in the economy, its potential for innovation, increased transparency, and its potential for cost savings. In confines of LECs, various players contribute to GAIA-X so that the local energy manager has access to both supply and demand data: local energy producers, small and medium consumers, external information based on weather, power prices providers.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** Energy production plant data (e.g., pump status, temperature levels) and measured values (e.g., electricity and heat quantities) can be securely transferred from the quarter's production plants to a GAIA-X-based cloud infrastructure. There the data is transferred into schedules for the systems and communicated back to the systems together with forecasts of future consumption and production.

6. OPENDEI⁹

Primary goals: (i) To create common data platforms regarding Manufacturing, Agriculture, Energy and Health topics based on a unified architecture and an established standard. (ii) To detect gaps, encourage synergies, support regional and national cooperation, and enhance communication among the Innovation Actions implementing the EU Digital Transformation strategy. The domains that OPENDEI focuses together with the correlated primary goals are: (i) **Manufacturing:** (a) To create Agile Value Networks for lot size 1 production: to design / manufacture customized products through more dynamic solutions. (b) To promote excellence in manufacturing: Data driven products and services to implement Zero Defect Manufacturing in Industry 4.0. (c) To enhance the human factor: designing the future workplace enhancing the collaboration between humans and autonomous systems. (d) To stimulate Sustainable Value Networks: applying the principles of circular economy to manufacturing processes. (ii) **Agrifood:** (a) To create a trust environment on new technologies. (b) To foresee the introduction of standards for data management and exchange of information. (c) To test/validate interoperability solutions (among Platforms and informative systems). (iii) **Energy:** (a) To allow for exchanges between market players (generators, aggregators, consumers, and any other player). (b) To support the vertical and horizontal integration of energy systems and the relaying of information with the market. (c) To enhance the physical system layer, which consists of automated energy infrastructures (generation, power conversion, storage, and networks) designed to meet citizen needs. (d) To enhance the digital infrastructure layer, which supports network operations to manage the integrated energy systems with higher levels of automation. (iv) **Healthcare:** (a) To introduce trusted big data solutions and cybersecurity for health and care and for a fair data economy in health and care. (b) Open eco-systems and related governance principles to support innovation in health and care; (c) To deploy robotics, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and autonomous systems for healthcare (including social robots); (d) To enable cross-cutting technologies, e.g., testing devices, wearables, Internet of Things (IoT), to address healthcare at the point of need (in the community, at home or in the move).

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** in the boundaries of creation of a common data space for sharing and pooling agricultural data from EC, OPEN DEI project includes data from weather

⁹ <https://www.opendei.eu/>

apps and drones which help to optimize harvesting methods, promoting digital solutions for fertilization.

- **Smart meter energy data:** A whole Energy Data Space affiliates to GAIA-X association as a working group. Under the Smart Living Use Case. Different actors, such as energy providers, municipalities, weather services or tourism associations, are networked in the Data Space and possess different data (such as solar energy data, household data or data on current bed occupancy). Individual use cases, such as energy communities or energy surplus distribution, are processed in the form of Data Circles. This is where secure and trusted data sharing takes place. Individual stakeholders can also collaborate in multiple Data Circles with different stakeholders and different data sets.

7. FIWARE¹⁰

Primary goals: (i) To promote an open-source cloud platform with a collaborative and mature ecosystem of developers, innovation Hubs, accelerators, cities and more than 1000 SMEs and start-ups. (ii) Promote open-source platforms to the domains: (a) Smart Cities Concept: Efficient infrastructure with an information network, eco-friendly mobility, creativity, and high productivity. With FIWARE, cities can achieve this transformation with minimum effort but great impact, by adopting common standard APIs and information models. (b) Smart Agrifood: Smart Farming aims to optimise production on farms by using the most modern means in a sustainable way, thereby increasing production, and delivering the best products in terms of quality while maximizing the return. It makes use of a wide range of technologies including IoT sensors, wearables, GPS services, UAVs, robots, and drones operating in the field which provide real-time data to systems helping to monitor the production line and support decisions. (c) Smart Energy: Introducing standardized, reusable, and quickly deployable models to design the necessary smart energy architectures and deploy solutions and applications flexible enough to enable these new production and consumption participative market models. (d) Smart Industry: Brings support to decisions and the automation of business processes. (e) Smart Water: delivers the necessary open standards that ease the integration of legacy and heterogeneous systems, supports decision making and brings innovative water digital solutions to the market throughout the water cycle including sources, abstraction, distribution, consumption, and treatment in relation to the underlying territory.

In FIWARE, a digital twin is an entity which digitally represents a real-world physical asset (e.g., a bus in a city, a milling machine in a factory) or a concept (e.g., a weather forecast, a product order).

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** (i) Smart Cities Domain: The processing of current real-time and historical data to extract valuable insights that can aid cities in their smart decisions and planning. A broad directory of cities all over the world are included, demonstrating real-time information about weather data (e.g., Athenian Marinas, weather data and sea conditions, notifications for extreme weather events or maritime incidents, associated with the Marinas, In regard of Sain-Quanin's stadiums, watering based on weather data, etc.). (ii) Agrifood Domain: Provides weather data through smart and connected products to the system of systems for the Farm Management System. Thus, Weather data system is formed, consisting by: Rain, humidity, temperature, sensors, Weather maps, Weather forecasts. (iii) Smart Energy Domain: Interfacing with IoT sensors, meters, or other devices (e.g., weather information for PV production, wind

¹⁰ <https://www.fiware.org/>

turbines etc.). Several research and innovation initiatives have demonstrated how, leveraging on the FIWARE Context Broker, data from power-plants, energy “smart-meters”, weather forecasts, and other sources, can be aggregated and produce the most up to date “intel” of the context they are operating into, to energy producers and consumers. (iv) Smart Industry Domain: Smart Factories can better exploit data from customers, suppliers, and partners nearby or around the globe. Non-manufacturing context data (e.g., from fleets, traffic and weather during product delivery) are used under this FIWARE domain to optimize inbound and outbound processes. (v) Smart Water Domain: Information about weather is given to IDAS NGSI Agent Framework.

- **Smart meter energy data:** FIWARE provides and considers the data from devices and systems pluggable in powered by FIWARE architectures via NGSI standard interfaces they offer: “FIWARE-Ready” devices (IoT sensors, robotic systems, machines) and software systems are able to provide and consume context/digital twin data following the NGSI open standard, therefore being able to integrate “plug&play” with any “Powered by FIWARE” smart solution. FIWARE-Ready devices/systems supporting same standard smart data models can be replaceable, this way avoiding vendor lock-in.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** In confines of smart meters, data associated with cooling and heating are also exploited. Several tools developed under FIWARE provide thermal/cooling data, e.g., *Miluz* is a datalogger that makes able to communicate with different Power Management industrial devices such as Power Consumption Meters, Electric Analysers, Frequency Variators or PV Inverters. *Miluz* can extract the data by Modbus Protocol and send it through FIWARE protocol; *SENSIoT* is a platform that has been built and scaled-up to be capable of ingesting a large amount of information gathered from all sort of Urbaser’s assets (vehicles, rubbish bins, industrial machines, electric meters, water meters, etc.) using electronic devices and sensors and later transmitted using several possible technologies (2G/3G/4G, MQTT, HTTPS, Sigfox, LoRaWAN, NB-IoT, OPC, industrial protocols).
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** platforms and tools developed for electricity consumption data for industrial and domestic sector.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** digital twins have been developed for enhanced flexibility asset.
- **Specific load control:** non-applicable.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** tools developed under FIWARE, which provide data for wind and PV: *SENSIoT* and *Miluz*.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** (i) Data about different product assets and EVs are included; (ii) Several use cases in smart cities domain demonstrate data for EV charging.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** Smart energy under FIWARE is a cost-effective, sustainable, and secure system in which renewable energy production, infrastructure and consumption are integrated and coordinate through energy services, active users and enabling technologies.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

8. SYNERGY¹¹

Primary goals: (i) It aims to develop a cutting-edge Big Data platform powered by energy-related data, addressing the intricacies of the energy/electricity sector value chain interactions. This platform will

¹¹ <https://synergyh2020.eu/>

enable the delivery of innovative Energy-as-a-Service offerings through extensive experimentation with big data analytics, service composition, data sharing, assets reuse, and business value generation. (ii) The project focuses on integrating existing big data technologies, tools, and libraries with legacy systems and ICT-enabled assets in the energy sector. This integration accelerates the data management and analysis cycle, transforming the four Big Data V's (Volume, Velocity, Variety, and Veracity) into tangible stakeholder value within the SYNERGY platform. (iii) It aims to establish secure, privacy-preserving, and intellectual property rights (IPR) respecting multi-party data exchange and sharing framework. This framework fosters the creation of a collaborative venture among data owners and analytics providers. (iv) The project seeks to deliver value-added services that meet the evolving needs of stakeholders in the energy sector. These services contribute to the realization of short, mid, and long-term targets for a cleaner, more sustainable, and efficient energy system, characterized by increased integration of renewable energy sources, enhanced energy efficiency, empowered consumers, and democratized energy markets. (v) Drives the establishment of novel collaborative business models centered around big data sharing and analytics services, benefiting the entire value chain of actors involved in the electricity domain. (vi) Aims to deliver a reference architecture and implementation of a big data platform for the electricity data value chain. The validity of this platform will be demonstrated through representative, large-scale, and enduring demonstrations. (vii) Focuses on promoting the widespread adoption of the SYNERGY solution as a next-generation Big Data Platform for data sharing-based Energy-as-a-Service applications. This objective will be achieved through extensive dissemination and knowledge transfer of the project's outcomes to the targeted stakeholders.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Smart meter energy data:** data from 71,500 smart meters, with resolution varying from 5 seconds to 15 minutes.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** IoT Sensing Data from Buildings (Temperature, Humidity, CO₂, Luminance, VOC, Submetering, Smart Devices).
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** IoT Sensing Data from Buildings (Temperature, Humidity, CO₂, Luminance, VOC, Submetering, Smart Devices).
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** non-applicable.
- **Specific load control:** data from BEMS.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** meter of renewable energy sources, SCADA, and data from PV inverters.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** meter of renewable energy sources, SCADA, and data from PV inverters.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** market data with special focus on imbalance Market related data as IPTO is the responsible entity for the operation and the settlement of the Market.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.
- **Other remarks:** there is SmaSCADA/EMS datasets from the different primary substations in the transmission network. RTU level datasets associated with the operation of the generation entities at the HV level. Demand and generation forecasts at the different layers (primary substation level) of the network, IPTO is responsible for.

9. BD4OPEN (Big Data for Innovative and Sustainable Energy Solutions)¹²

Primary goals: BD4OPEN aims to leverage advanced big-data techniques such as machine learning, deep learning, artificial intelligence (AI), and forecasting to acquire knowledge and create services for effectively managing electrical distribution grids. The project utilizes big data from five European data providers, including distribution system operators (DSOs), microgrids, and electric vehicle charging infrastructures. These datasets are processed using an AI-based analytic toolbox that is hosted on the project marketplace. The resulting output from this data processing enables service providers to develop innovative services and establish connections back to the original data providers, fostering a collaborative ecosystem.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:**
- **Smart meter energy data:** the “ESTEBANELL ENERGIA pilot/VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” use case: Smart meters. **Derived services** – Observability: Process to determine the actual observability LV network based on fact (smart metering) not current theory.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:**
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** the “ESTEBANELL ENERGIA pilot/VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” pilot and “EleKtro Celje” pilot: Consumer profiles (patterns & consumption) and client clustering.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** the “ESTEBANELL ENERGIA” pilot / “OEDAS” pilot / “VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” pilot / “EleKtro Celje” pilot: SCADA, GIS, Analysers, Large scale battery
Derived services: (i) **EV to Grid:** Analysis of huge amounts of driver data will be collected to estimate the flexibility EVs can bring to the grid. (ii) **Flexibility forecasting:** Predicting flexibility from small generators/energy storage systems/prosumers.
- **Specific load control:** the “OEDAS” pilot / “VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” pilot: Energy storage infrastructure. **Derived Services** – Loads, generation, energy storage management at individual household or at community level: Analysis of smart meter data and demand response strategies to impact on customer behaviour. Demand estimation; raising household consumer awareness about the impact of their behaviour on load profiles through smart meters.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** the “ESTEBANELL ENERGIA” pilot / “OEDAS” pilot / “VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” pilot / “EleKtro Celje” pilot: PV generation, wind generation (OEDAS).
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** “OEDAS” pilot: Hydro, Geo-thermal; “VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL” pilot: EV charging; “NUVVE” pilot: EV data; EV charging infrastructure data; “EleKtro Celje” pilot: Hydro generation.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** Flexibility aggregated Service (BRPs): use of algorithms to support decision making based on technic and economic criteria.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** “ESTEBANELL ENERGIA” pilot: EV charging infrastructure data; topology & observability of LV or MV network.
- **Other remarks:** list of data shared by pilot and related development services.

10. BDVA (Big Data Value Association)¹³

¹² <https://bd4open.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.bdva.eu/>

Primary goals: The project is focused on achieving multiple objectives. (i) It aims to achieve broader access to data to fully unlock the potential of emerging AI technology. This will be accomplished through the design and implementation of a common, trustworthy, and decentralized data space that facilitates safe and democratic data sharing, thereby fostering growth in the European data economy. (ii) The project aims to establish a European-governed data space, positioning Europe as a leading force in steering international efforts to develop data and AI solutions that align with European ethical values, including democracy, privacy protection, and equality. (iii) The project seeks to develop an Innovation Ecosystem that drives the data-driven digital transformation in Europe, yielding significant economic and societal benefits and ensuring Europe's sustained leadership in creating value from big data and artificial intelligence. (iv) The project strives to enable the digital transformation of the economy and society through advancements in areas such as big data and AI technologies and services, data platforms and spaces, Industrial AI, data-driven value creation, standardization, and the cultivation of relevant skills.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** There are “i-Spaces” that are labelled by BDVA that have links with VC's. However, BDVA itself seems to not be directly linked with any of the VC's.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** BDVA is involved in many attempts to share and collect data from different domains. One data space particularly interesting for DATA CELLAR Horizon is the "European Green Deal data space": A common marketplace for data, algorithms and applications from and for businesses, consumers, government and citizens, connecting *public and private data ecosystems and enabling public and private stakeholders to access, process and reuse relevant data across borders* and sectors within the established circles of trust.

11. PLATOON¹⁴

Primary goals: The project's core objective is to leverage the PLATOON reference architecture for the development and implementation of scalable and replicable energy management solutions. These solutions are designed to actively contribute to the advancement of various key goals, including the promotion of increased renewable energy consumption, effective management of smart grids, improved energy efficiency, and optimized management of energy assets. To support these efforts, relevant data sources encompass a range of crucial information, which may include renewable energy generation data, smart grid performance metrics, energy consumption data, and comprehensive data on energy assets.

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** historical data from different pilots were used to develop the related services.
- **Smart meter energy data:** from the third pilot (to develop a tool for the quantification of losses in the distribution grid of a DSO and the detection of non-technical losses) – smart meter data from Sampol's smart grid in ParcBit, Majorca (Spain). From the fifth pilot: data collected from the meters (power and gas, including 165 photovoltaics) and from available Energy Audits in Rome.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** from the fourth pilot: heating and cooling loads. From the fifth pilot: buildings heating and cooling energy consumption dataset.

¹⁴ <https://platoon-project.eu/>

- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** from the third pilot: prosumer segmentation based on clustering techniques applied to their load profiles (not an input but an outcome of the pilot).
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** non-applicable.
- **Specific load control:** from the third pilot: to develop a predictive maintenance tool for LV/MV transformers using available data from Sampol's smart grid in ParcBit, Majorca (Spain). Database with transformer information and measurements, and maintenance logs. Gather historical load data, at the MV substation level.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** From the first pilot (data from wind turbines): high frequency (kHz range) detailed measurements; lower frequency SCADA data (10-min) and status logs; load history of the electrical components; From the second pilot data from IMP proprietary SCADA system.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** non-applicable.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

12. Data Sharing Coalition¹⁵

Primary goals: The primary goals of the Data Sharing Coalition revolve around promoting (cross-sectoral) data sharing, under the control of the entitled party. This is achieved through the realization of data sharing

use cases, fostering interoperability between data spaces, and reinforcing individual initiatives. One particularly valuable use case is "benchmarking for industry associations," as it provides a harmonization framework that elaborates on design choices across various data sharing contexts. This serves as the basis for developing generic cross-domain agreements. Such an approach facilitates the design of a framework that enables data sharing among domains with differing data types (such as open versus closed data, yearly versus daily data streams, and sensitive versus non-sensitive data).

Relevant data:

- **Weather in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Smart meter energy data:** in the "green loan" use case, the consumer will be enabled to use their energy data to receive support with making their house more sustainable. This support can range from sustainability advice to a favourable "Green Loan" for investments in energy saving measures (e.g., heat pumps or solar cells). The consumer shares data on his or her energy consumption with an intermediary and/or loan provider, who in turn can assess potential savings from certain energy saving measures.
- **Thermal/cooling consumption of profiled end-users:** non-applicable.
- **Electricity consumption of profiled end-users:** in the "green loan" use case, the consumer will be enabled to use their energy data to receive support with making their house more sustainable. This support can range from sustainability advice to a favourable "Green Loan" for investments in energy saving measures (e.g., heat pumps or solar cells). The consumer shares data on his or her energy consumption with an intermediary and/or loan provider, who in turn can assess potential savings from certain energy saving measures.
- **Grid need for flexibility data:** non-applicable.

¹⁵ <https://datasharingcoalition.eu/>

- **Specific load control:** non-applicable.
- **Wind turbine/PV power in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Power production rate of different assets (i.e., hydro, biomass, CHP, EVs) in different EU locations:** non-applicable.
- **Energy costs (electricity, natural gas etc.):** the consumer can have more control over their energy data, as they can decide to use their data to access advice or attractive financial value propositions. With their new “green loans” and input for sustainability advice, financial institutes can support the transition to a more sustainable society.
- **Other data relevant to DATA CELLAR:** non-applicable.

In addition to the aforementioned fundamental dataspace under investigation, a selection of dataspace with relatively less impact on the DATA CELLAR is also presented:

13. NAPS - National Access Points¹⁶

Primary goals: The process of interlinking all transportation-related elements with the digital layer involves the establishment of a Digital Architecture. This architecture is built upon the principles of open and common standards and interfaces, as well as an efficient and secure data ecosystem. Its purpose is to facilitate seamless access, smooth exchange, and effective reuse of transport-related data, thereby supporting the provision of EU-wide interoperable travel and traffic services to end users. Furthermore, it aims to facilitate the establishment of connections between stakeholders involved in research, development, and the provision of such services.

14. PANTERA¹⁷

Primary goals: The project aims to establish a centralized repository within the European Union that serves as a comprehensive point of reference for project data, information, and knowledge pertaining to technologies that contribute to the energy transition. To ensure effective utilization and compatibility, the project advocates the use of standards to support interoperability and a common taxonomy. Additionally, the project focuses on developing supporting tools that enhance the overall process. Collaboration among relevant stakeholders is facilitated to foster collective efforts in achieving the energy transition goals. Moreover, the project aims to construct appropriate repositories of case studies that provide guidance to stakeholders on the effective utilization of the generated data, information, and knowledge.

15. INTERFACE¹⁸

Primary goals: (i) To create a common architecture that connects market platforms to establish a seamless pan-European electricity exchange linking wholesale and retail markets and allows all electricity market players to trade and procure energy services in a transparent, non-discriminatory way. (ii) To define and demonstrate standardised products, key parameters, and the activation and settlement process for energy services. (iii) To drive collaboration in the procurement of grid services by TSOs and DSOs, and to create strong incentives to connected customers, by improving market signals

INTERFACE

¹⁶ <https://napcore.eu/description-naps/>

¹⁷ <https://pantera-platform.eu/>

¹⁸ <http://www.interface.eu/>

and allowing them to procure services based on specific locations and grid conditions. (iv) To integrate small-scale and large-scale assets to increase market liquidity for grid services and facilitate scaling up of new services which are compatible across Europe. (v) To promote state-of-the-art digital technologies that consumers are familiar with in other everyday transactions (i.e., e-auctions, e-commerce, e-banking, social networks), into the electricity value chain, in order to engage end-users into next generation electricity market transactions, creating incomparable economic benefits by deferring conventional energy infrastructure investments. In addition, data for Grid need for flexibility are included; the project will design, develop, and exploit an Interoperable pan-European Grid Services Architecture (IEGSA) to act as the interface between the power system (TSO and DSO) and the customers and allow the seamless and coordinated operation of all stakeholders to use and procure common services. Finally, other data relevant to DATA CELLAR: state-of-the-art digital tools based on blockchains, and big data management will provide new opportunities for electricity market participation and thus engage consumers into the INTERRFACE proposed market structures that will be designed to exploit Distributed Energy Resources.

16. PLATONE¹⁹

Primary goals: the project aims to define new approaches to increase the observability of renewable energy resources and of the less predictable loads while exploiting their flexibility. Also, to develop advanced management platforms to unlock grid flexibility and to realize an open and non-discriminatory market, linking users, aggregators, and operators.

17. MyData Global²⁰

Primary goals: It is not necessarily a database. It is an approach to the management of personal data. The primary goal is to empower individuals by improving digital human rights and the right to self-determination with respect to personal data. The only use case of “MyData Global” that is potentially relevant for DATA CELLAR is the “Carbon Footprint” calculator. However, it is based on the food consumption of consumers.

18. Elhub²¹

Primary goals: Power suppliers and network companies rely on the measured values provided by Elhub as the foundation for billing electricity and network license fees to end customers across Norway. Elhub facilitates this process through the utilization of standardized interfaces and secure message exchange protocols. This not only enables efficient invoicing but also creates opportunities for the market to develop automated services that drive additional digitization and foster the implementation of intelligent solutions.

19. Fingrid Datahub²²

Primary goals: The main tasks of the Datahub are to provide and develop the centralised information exchange system and its other services and administer the registered information for electricity market needs. Pursuant to the Electricity Market

¹⁹ <https://www.platone-h2020.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.mydata.org/>

²¹ <https://elhub.no/en/>

²² <https://www.fingrid.fi/en/electricity-market/datahub/>

Act, information on electricity consumption, such as consumption and customer information of an accounting point will be transferred to a shared information exchange system called Datahub. A shared system will improve the service provided to an electricity consumer, since the parties can exchange information in real time. An electricity consumer can monitor the consumption information of their accounting points in a single system, independently of DSOs or electricity suppliers. Information security and privacy are ensured, and information can only be accessed by the parties entitled to do so. When all information can be found in a single location, it is also easier to trace.

20. DataHub (EnergiNet)²³

Primary goals: The purpose of DataHub is to ensure uniform communication and standardized processes for the professional players who act on the Danish electricity market - all with a view to creating better competition and improving conditions for electricity customers.

21. Copernicus climate data store²⁴

Primary goals: to provide a single point of access to a wide range of quality-assured climate assets, and to provide a set of tools for analysing and predicting the impacts of climate change. The dataspace also demonstrates:

Weather in different EU locations: Different datasets are available. In particular, the dataset "Near surface meteorological variables from 1979 to 2019 derived from bias-corrected reanalysis" provides bias-corrected reconstruction of near-surface meteorological variables derived from the fifth generation of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) atmospheric reanalyses (ERA5). It is intended to be used as a meteorological forcing dataset for land surface and hydrological models.

22. ENTSO-e transparency platform²⁵

Primary goals: The platform aims to increase the transparency, which is essential for the implementation of the Internal Electricity Market (IEM) and for the creation of efficient, liquid, and competitive wholesale markets.

It is also critical for creating a level playing field between market participants and avoiding the scope for market power (if it exists) to be abused. This platform enables the provision of the required electricity market information for the future and further facilitates the development of efficient and competitive energy markets across Europe. Such developments support the steady evolution of electricity markets across Europe in terms of integration, competition.

23. openEntrance²⁶

Primary goals: The project aims at developing, using, and disseminating an open, transparent, and integrated modelling platform for assessing low-carbon transition pathways in Europe. openEntrance provides also other data relevant to DATA CELLAR: It is a modelling platform for assessing low-carbon transition pathways in Europe. The term "scenario data" in this context can refer to any quantitative data related to a better understanding of the

²³ <https://energinet.dk/Energidata/DataHub/>

²⁴ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>

²⁵ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>

²⁶ <https://openentrance.eu/>

energy transition and societal objectives on alternative pathways towards a climate-neutral society. This includes scenario results from numerical models, historical timeseries data, input data and structured assumptions for model calibration, or data from relevant surveys. Other remarks: In T7.2 (EDF lead) advanced functions in EDF openENTRANCE dataspace will be implemented enabling the interconnection openENTRANCE with DATA CELLAR. EDF will perform studies via openENTRANCE to be able to demonstrate that DATA CELLAR will enable to investigate the impact of local energy communities on EU energy systems.

24. ihan²⁷

Primary goals: (i) To develop a human-driven European data market, where companies that use data responsibly and open-mindedly succeed with smart services. (ii) Transfer data between systems in Finland and Estonia (system home country). (iii) To share data more freely between different parties. (iv) To promote access to more targeted services that improve customers' well-being and daily lives, while stimulating companies' (of all sizes) growth through innovation and well-being increase. (v) To engage companies in building a fair data economy. (vi) To provide people with tools that they can use to influence the use of their data online. In addition, the information category weather in different EU locations: The Farmidata pilot developed under IHAN project in the Salo area evaluated IT development needs in agriculture and assessed what kinds of opportunities are presented by digitisation. The necessary applications were then be developed based on the studies and the structure of the ecosystem was designed. The pilot consisted of three trials: Farmimapping, Farmistore, Farmisää (Farm weather). The Farmisää (Farm Weather) pilot defined a micro-weather network from real-time weather and soil data. IoT sensors produced more precise weather data than before and monitored the soil.

25. ONENET²⁸

Primary goals: (i) To develop an open and flexible architecture for transforming the actual European electricity system, which is often managed in fragmented country – or area – level, in a pan-European smarter and more efficient one; (ii) To reciprocally coordinate market and network technical operations closer to real time: (a) Among them; (b) Across different countries; (c) While maximizing the consumer capabilities to participate in an open market structure. (iii) To design an open IT architecture supported by scalable data management enabling the market structures; (iv) To verify in a set of large field tests the concepts and solutions proposed; (v) To promote the results of OneNet in the standardization process for a significant market uptake.

3.2. Influence of Databases/Dataspaces towards Ontology Development

To establish a comprehensive and precise ontology, it is important to leverage relevant databases, such as energy, environment-related repositories, and linked data. These sources of information not only inform the ontology development process but also stimulate it by providing valuable insights and up-to-date knowledge about these domains. One of the key benefits of using relevant databases is the access to energy and environment-related repositories. These repositories are dedicated to collecting and organizing data pertaining to energy and/or environmental data. They act as valuable

²⁷ <https://www.sitra.fi/en/topics/fair-data-economy/>

²⁸ <https://onenet-project.eu/>

resources for the DATA CELLAR ontology developers, as they provide a wealth of information about the entities, attributes, and relationships that exist within these domains.

Furthermore, linked data plays a significant role in supporting ontology development. Linked data refers to a method of publishing and connecting structured data on digital forms (i.e., online databases, dedicated servers, etc.), following standardized formats and using semantic technologies. By leveraging linked data, DATA CELLAR ontology developers can access a vast network of interconnected datasets and knowledge graphs, which can enrich the ontology development process. When incorporating relevant databases and linked data into the ontology development process, it is essential to ensure that the information gathered reflects the most current and accurate understanding of the domain. Databases and linked data sources often undergo updates and revisions, incorporating new research findings, insights, and discoveries. By regularly consulting and integrating these updated sources, ontology developers can ensure that the ontology remains aligned with the latest knowledge in the domain. This iterative process of data integration and ontology refinement helps to maintain the relevance and accuracy of the ontology over time. Moreover, the utilization of relevant databases and linked data can also facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing among the DATA CELLAR energy experts and ontology developers. These sources of information provide a common ground for stakeholders to exchange insights, validate assumptions, and contribute to the ontology development process. By involving domain experts and leveraging their expertise, ontology developers can refine the ontology's structure and content, ensuring that it accurately represents the nuances and complexities of the domain.

In addition to informing and stimulating ontology development, relevant databases and linked data also contribute to the evaluation and validation of the ontology. Once an initial version of the ontology is developed, it can be compared and aligned with the data available in the databases and linked data sources. This process allows the DATA CELLAR ontology developers to identify any discrepancies, gaps, or inconsistencies between the ontology and the actual data. By iteratively refining the ontology based on the insights gained from these comparisons, the developers can ensure that the ontology accurately reflects the real-world domain it aims to represent.

4. Ontology Methodology

In the field of knowledge-based systems, the creation of a domain model, or ontology, plays crucial role in the development process. The benefits of these ontologies are well documented, including facilitating knowledge sharing and reuse, as well as improving the engineering of knowledge-based systems through enhanced acquisition, verification, and maintenance processes. In contrast, the data from multiple sources are effectively managed via dataspace systems. Ontologies can be used in *databases* and *dataspaces* to provide a semantic framework for organizing and linking data and information. By incorporating an ontology into a dataspace, the relationships between data elements can be made explicit and can be used to enhance data search, retrieval, and integration (see Section 3.2).

Section 0 presents the proposed methodology concerning ontology development to be applied for the DATA CELLAR energy domain and in relation with Section 0. The DATA CELLAR methodology is based primarily on the **Linked Open Terms (LOT)**²⁹ methodology, and partially on the **METHONTOLOGY**³⁰. The fundamental process steps of both methodologies are principally complementary, including the activities of **(i) Specification**, **(ii) Implementation** and **Conceptualization**, and **(iii) Maintenance** and **(iv) Evaluation** of the resulting ontology. Additionally, METHONTOLOGY, together with other traditional ontology methodologies are reused, and proposed to be followed as part of LOT when the techniques are applicable³¹. **It is worth mentioning that some parts of the methodology have been adapted, or specialized for the DATA CELLAR needs and are documented in the corresponding sections.**

4.1. Fundamental Ontological Definitions

Prior to the analysis of the methodology, an initial insight on the ontology core terminology and the fundamental definitions used in this deliverable is indicated.

4.1.1. What is the meaning of the “ontology” term?

Different meanings in different communities are attributed to the term “ontology”. Commonly two specific uses are appended to the ontology term, an *immeasurable* and a *measurable* one:

The former case concerns the philosophical domain, indicating the study of the nature of existence, including the categories and structures of objects, properties, events, processes, and relationships in all realms of reality. The term “ontology” is generally used interchangeably with “metaphysics,” which was a label applied by early students of Aristotle referring to what Aristotle himself described to as “first philosophy”³². In this domain, the ontology term is sometimes used in a wider scope addressing the “what could potentially exist” inquiry, followed by using “metaphysics” regarding which of the various alternative possible ontologies represent the reality. The first recorded use of

²⁹ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

³⁰ Gomez-Perez, Asuncion & Fernández-López, Mariano & Corcho, Oscar. (2004). *Ontological Engineering: With Examples from the Areas of Knowledge Management, E-Commerce and the Semantic Web*.

³¹ M. Poveda-Villalón, A. Fernández-Izquierdo, M. Fernández-López, R. García-Castro, LOT: An industrial oriented ontology engineering framework, *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, Volume 111, 2022, DOI: 10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755.

³² Guarino N., Oberle D., Staab S., “What is an Ontology?”, *Handbook on Ontologies*, 1-17, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-92673-3_0

"ontology" in English, as documented by the Oxford English Dictionary, appeared in Bailey's dictionary of 1721, which defined ontology as "an account of being in the abstract"³³.

The countable definition of ontology is principally encountered in the field of Computer Science. In this case, the ontology is defined as a special kind of information object or computational artifact. Concerning the AI systems, the inquiry of what "exists" is the one that can be represented. Via the measurable definition of ontologies, one can properly shape the structure of a system relevant entities and relations that emerge from its observations. An ontology's foundation is formed by a hierarchy of concepts that involve generalization and specialization, which is commonly known as a **taxonomy**.

Five core definitions have been given to ontologies, with the ones developed by Neches and Studer being the most applicable to the DATA CELLAR concept. The former "**defines as ontology a set of representational primitives with which a domain of knowledge or discourse are modeled**"³⁴. The second identifies that "**an ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization**"³⁵.

Due to the problems linked with heterogeneous data, different definitions, and incompatible models of many domains, including the field of energy systems analysis, it is hard for results to be re-used, and models to be coupled. In this context, **ontologies provide a precisely defined vocabulary to build a common and shared conceptualization of the energy domain**.

4.1.2. Taxonomies

Taxonomies play a vital role in conceptual modelling and have gained even greater significance with the advent of the extended Entity-Relationship model³⁶. Well-organized taxonomies serve as a powerful tool for bringing coherence and structure to the various model components. They are particularly valuable in presenting focused perspectives of a model that can be easily understood by humans. Moreover, they are instrumental in facilitating the reuse and integration of ontological elements. Conversely, poorly constructed taxonomies have an adverse impact, leading to confusion and hindering the reusability and integration of models.

The development approach of the DATA CELLAR revolves around employing literary resources to construct a highly detailed taxonomy that places significant emphasis on analyzing the intrinsic attributes that constitute taxonomic associations, rather than focusing primarily on the semantic aspects of the relationship itself³⁷. This concept is effectively communicated through the consideration of the proposition " φ subsumes ϕ ," which implies the act of one entity being encompassed by another:

$$\forall x \varphi(x) \rightarrow \phi(x)$$

33 Smith B., "Ontology", *Furniture of the world*, 47-68, DOI: 10.1163/9789401207799_005

34 Neches, R.; Fikes, R.; Finin, T.; Gruber, T.; Patil, R.; Senator, T.; Swartout, W.R. *Enabling Technology for Knowledge Sharing*. *AI Magazine*. Winter 1991. 36-56

35 Studer, Benjamins, Fensel. *Knowledge Engineering: Principles and Methods*. *Data and Knowledge Engineering*. 25 (1998) 161-197

36 Elmasri, R., Weeldreyer, J., and Hevner, A. 1985. *The category concept: An extension to the Entity-Relationship model*. *Data and Knowledge Engineering*, 1(1): 75-11

37 Guarino, N., Welty, C. (2000). *Ontological Analysis of Taxonomic Relationships*. In: Laender, A.H.F., Liddle, S.W., Storey, V.C. (eds) *Conceptual Modeling — ER 2000*. *ER 2000. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 1920. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45393-8_16

Taxonomies serve a crucial purpose in organizing ontologies, promoting human comprehension, and enabling seamless integration. Within the context of DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology, the taxonomies predominantly comprise *rigid properties* that are indispensable to all instances (e.g., $\forall x \varphi(x) \rightarrow \varphi(x)$). These properties are commonly considered primitive due to the inherent challenges associated with their precise definition, such as the notion of an entity, or a fundamental entity.

4.1.3. Databases, Dataspaces & their Relationship with Ontologies

A **database** can be conceptualized as a **sophisticated system that acquires, organizes, and administers data in a structured manner**, facilitating proficient retrieval and manipulation of information. The data housed within a database pertains to distinct facets of the comprehensive data model. Databases can be tailored to accommodate diverse data models, including relational, hierarchical, or object-oriented, and can be accessed through an array of languages and interfaces, thereby offering versatility in data management and utilization³⁸.

The term **dataspace** describes **a concept referring to a virtual space or environment where data from multiple sources can be accessed, integrated, and analysed in a unified manner**. Dataspaces overcome the limitations of traditional databases, which often bear rigid data schemas and are usually limited to single domains. They enable the integration of heterogeneous data from various sources, such as databases, web services, file systems, into a single virtual space, without the need for extensive data modelling or schema design³⁹.

Databases and **dataspaces** are used in conjunction with ontologies facilitating the organization and storage of information, through different structures and purposes⁴⁰. Databases are designed to store and retrieve large amounts of data efficiently, while dataspaces allow great flexibility and scalability. Ontologies are designed to represent knowledge in a specific domain in a structured and hierarchical way. However, there can be a relationship between those definitions, occurred as a progression towards a more comprehensive and flexible way of managing and organizing large amounts of data. Together, these three concepts form a robust framework for managing and integrating heterogeneous data from multiple sources and are widely used in a variety of applications and industries to enable data-driven decision making and provide valuable insights. As data continues to grow in complexity and size, the combination of databases, dataspaces, and ontologies is likely to become increasingly important in managing and organizing this data in a consistent and effective manner.

The DATA CELLAR creates a public dataspace, easy to be populated and interact with other EU energy dataspace exploits and implements the terms to provide facilitations to the LEC stakeholders.

38 Debra Zahay, Abbie Griffin, Elisa Fredericks, *Sources, uses, and forms of data in the new product development process*, *Industrial Marketing Management*, 2004, Pages 657-666, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2003.10.002>.

39 N. Schahovska, Y. Syerov, "Web-community ontological representation using intelligent dataspace analyzing agent," 2009 10th International Conference - The Experience of Designing and Application of CAD Systems in Microelectronics, Lviv, Ukraine, 2009, pp. 479-480.

40 Kontchakov, Roman & Lutz, Carsten & Toman, David & Wolter, Frank & Zakharyashev, Michael. (2011). *The Combined Approach to Ontology-Based Data Access*. *IJCAI*. 2656-2661. 10.5591/978-1-57735-516-8/IJCAI11-442.

4.1.4. Metadata

Metadata as a term was first referred in 1968 by Philip R. Bagley in a technical report titled “Extension of Programming Language Concept”⁴¹. A search on the term “metadata” in the International Organization for Standardization’s Online Browsing Platform (ISO OBP) reveals that there are 96 separate ISO standards that provide definitions regarding the term. Based on their principal, **metadata refer to data that provide information about other data**. Thus, metadata is “**data about data**” and can include a wide variety of information, such as format, size, location, date, etc. Metadata address the *who, what, when, where, and why* of these data. In regard of DATA CELLAR, the D2.1 – “DATA CELLAR inventory via “What, Why, Where, How and Types” approach and first dataset from VCs to populate DATA CELLAR” provides an initial overview of the metadata.

Metadata are considered of high importance since they assist on providing meaning to data. Metadata facilitate organizing and categorizing data, searching, and discovering them, providing important information about the data for analysis and interpretation. Metadata are used in a wide range of applications, including library cataloguing, scientific research, data management and web search engines. They should be designed in a way that machines can easily search and use them, which means they should be machine actionable. By adding metadata, the data can be stored for later use. Metadata can be either general or specific to a particular field, such as the Dublin Core⁴² for general metadata, or domain experts can define specific metadata for their field.

There are several types of metadata, including descriptive metadata, administrative metadata, technical metadata, and structural metadata:

- Descriptive metadata provides information about the content of data, such as its title, author, and date of creation.
- Administrative metadata includes information about the ownership, rights, and permissions associated with data.
- Technical metadata provides information about the format, encoding, and storage of data.
- Structural metadata provides information about the relationships between different data elements.

Metadata can be stored in a variety of formats, such as XML, RDF, or JSON. It can be embedded within data files or stored in separate metadata files.

Within the information included in metadata is the position of the dataset in a relevant taxonomy, which is a method to structure the knowledge related to a discipline into topics. The most pertinent paradigm used as a taxonomy is considered the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (i.e., green taxonomy)⁴³. It is a classification system established to clarify which investments are environmentally sustainable, in the context of the EU Green Deal.

41 J. Greenberg (2009) “Understanding Metadata and Metadata Schemes”, *Journal of Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* https://doi.org/10.1300/J104v40n03_02

42 DCMI Metadata Terms. Available online: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

43 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/EU_taxonomy_for_sustainable_activities

4.1.5. Data and metadata Schemas

At the core of any database lies its data schema, which serves as the foundation for organizing, storing, and accessing data. A **data schema is essentially a blueprint or structure that outlines how data is stored and processed within a database**. It specifies the types of data that can be stored, the format in which the data will be stored, and the relationships between various data elements. Beyond these fundamental details, a data schema often includes rules for data collection, validation, and transformation to ensure that data is consistent, accurate, and usable. A well-designed data schema is crucial for effective data management since it facilitates the organization and management of data, which is vital for ensuring data quality.

Data schemas provide a formal structure for organizing and storing data, defining the types of data that can be stored, the format in which the data is stored, and the relationships between different data elements. This is particularly important in ontology development, where a well-designed data schema can facilitate the creation and management of ontological concepts, relationships, and attributes.

Effective use of metadata and data schemas in ontology development requires a clear understanding of the domain and data being modeled, as well as the intended use of the ontology. This involves identifying the relevant metadata for each data element and developing a data schema that accurately captures the relationships between different data elements.

A variety of data schemas exist, such as relational, object-oriented, hierarchical, and document-oriented schemas. A properly designed schema enables efficient access and analysis of data by both applications and users. As such, a well-constructed data schema is essential for ensuring accurate and reliable data management.

4.1.6. Knowledge Graphs

Knowledge representation and reasoning, drawing inspiration from human problem-solving approaches, aim to encode knowledge to empower intelligent systems in solving complex tasks⁴⁴. In recent times, knowledge graphs have emerged as a structured embodiment of human knowledge, attracting significant attention from both academic and industrial spheres. **A knowledge graph serves as a systematic representation of factual information, comprising entities, relationships, and semantic descriptions**. Entities can encompass tangible objects in the real world as well as abstract concepts, while relationships denote the connections between entities. The semantic descriptions associated with entities and relationships provide well-defined meanings, encompassing types and properties. Widely adopted variants such as property graphs, or attributed graphs incorporate additional properties, or attributes, assigned to nodes and relations, further enriching the representational capacity of knowledge graphs. The knowledge graphs are exploited in this deliverable to represent the nodes and interactions of the different proposed DATA CELLAR semantic ontologies, and in this case, it is developed via the exploitation of semantic framework platforms.

⁴⁴ A. Newell, J. C. Shaw, and H. A. Simon, "Report on a general problem-solving program," in *Proc. IFIP Congr.*, vol. 256, 1959, p. 64.

4.2. Ontology-based Languages/Frameworks

An ontology can be defined as a highly abstracted and comprehensive framework of a particular domain that captures its data structure along with the interrelationships among the relevant entities. It is possible to define rules on top of the ontology, thereby enhancing its usability. However, as the use of ontologies has become more widespread, the challenge of reconciling divergent ontologies that pertain to the same domain has emerged as an issue that needs to be addressed.

OWL (Web Ontology Language) is a linguistically formalized ontology language that has been codified by the World Wide Web Consortium and demonstrates considerable popularity and usage across a wide range of domains. SWRL (Semantic Web Rule Language) extends the capabilities of OWL by providing a powerful rule-based mechanism for reasoning about knowledge and data in the Semantic Web. Via SWRL, complex rules and logical constraints enabling the inference of new knowledge or validation of existing knowledge within an ontology can be created. These rules can be used to enhance the reasoning capabilities of Semantic Web applications, check the consistency of ontologies, validate data instances, and identify errors or inconsistencies in data. In contrast, Frame Logic (F-Logic)⁴⁵ is an ontology language that is recognized by several corporations, although it was originally created for the purposes of deductive and object-oriented databases. RDF (Resource Description Framework) is characterized by its ability to describe and model metadata about resources on the web, facilitating the exchange and integration of data across diverse applications and systems. RDF provides a formalized, machine-understandable syntax for representing knowledge and data on the web, thereby enabling automated reasoning and decision-making. It leverages the principles of graph-based modeling to represent data as a network of interconnected nodes, each of which is associated with a unique identifier and a set of properties that describe its attributes and relationships to other nodes in the graph. RDF is a flexible and extensible language that can accommodate a wide variety of data types and schemas, making it a popular choice for building semantically enriched applications and knowledge-based systems.

Ontologies may have different models that hinder automatic alignment, regardless of being written in the same ontology language. In such scenarios, users must define mappings between these heterogeneous ontologies manually. To address the issue, the **RDF framework was used in confines of DATA CELLAR**. A comprehensive description of the ontology frameworks is given:

4.2.1. OWL (Web Ontology Language)

The current iteration of the Web Ontology Language, OWL 2, is an evolutionary extension of the original OWL specification from 2004. OWL is built on top of RDF (Resource Description Framework)⁴⁶, including additional vocabulary with formal semantics. It has emerged as the de facto ontology language within the semantic web community, supported by an ever-expanding suite of applications. OWL is designed to capture rich and nuanced representations of knowledge about entities, sets of entities, and the interrelationships among them, empowering the creation, dissemination, and reuse of ontologies. With its ability to formally describe concepts and their interrelationships within a given domain, OWL endows documents with machine-understandable

⁴⁵ <https://dbpedia.org/page/F-logic> | About: F-Logic

⁴⁶ V. Sugumaran, Chapter 14 - Semantic technologies for enhancing knowledge management systems, *Successes and Failures of Knowledge Management*, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805187-0.00014-0>.

semantics. The formal underpinnings of OWL draw on Description Logics, a well-established knowledge representation formalism that has been subjected to extensive research scrutiny over the years.

There are three variations of OWL, with different expressiveness levels:

OWL DL: It is architected to maximize expressivity while still preserving computational completeness (i.e., the property that either φ or $\neg\varphi$ holds), decidability (i.e., the property that an effective process exists for determining whether φ is derivable), and the availability of practical reasoning algorithms. All OWL language constructs are included in OWL DL, but they are subject to various restrictions. For example, number restrictions may not be imposed on properties that are declared to be transitive. Similarly, while a class may be a subclass of several classes, it cannot simultaneously be an instance of another class. The reason for the "DL" moniker in OWL DL is that it aligns with description logic, a field of research that has extensively studied the logical foundations of OWL.

OWL Lite: Initially conceived to cater to the needs of users seeking to construct simple classification hierarchies and constraints, *OWL Lite* is a variant of OWL. Though it facilitates the enforcement of cardinality constraints, it does so exclusively for values of either zero or one. Akin to thesauri and other taxonomies, OWL Lite was designed to facilitate an expedited migration path for systems requiring limited expressivity, with the expectation that it would be easier to provide tool support for OWL Lite than for its more complex counterparts. However, in practice, most of the limitations imposed on OWL Lite amount to mere syntactic inconveniences, since most of the constructs available in OWL DL can be synthesized through intricate combinations of OWL Lite features. Consequently, the task of developing OWL Lite tools has proven to be nearly as arduous as the task of developing tools for OWL DL. As a result, OWL Lite has not gained widespread adoption.

OWL Full: In contrast to OWL Lite and OWL DL, OWL Full is founded on a distinct set of semantic principles and was developed with the aim of retaining some degree of interoperability with RDF Schema. In OWL Full, it is admissible to interpret a class as both a collection of individuals and as an individual entity. This feature is prohibited in OWL DL. OWL Full endows an ontology with the ability to amplify the meaning of the pre-defined RDF or OWL vocabulary. However, since OWL Full is undecidable, there is no reasoning tool capable of performing comprehensive reasoning tasks for it.

OWL 2 demonstrates three sublanguages, the (1) OWL 2 EL, the (2) OWL 2 QL, and the (3) OWL 2 RL⁴⁷. DATA CELLAR ontology harmonizes with the OWL 2 EL & QL, due to the numbers of classes and properties, together with implementation of mechanisms that enable efficient data retrieval and querying from dataspace.

The **OWL 2 QL** specification offers a robust set of fundamental features that are essential for the expression of complex conceptual models, such as those found in UML class diagrams. This profile represents the common subset of RDFS and OWL 2 DL and has been specifically engineered to allow for straightforward querying of data residing within standard relational database systems via ontology rewriting mechanisms.

⁴⁷ https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-profiles/#OWL_2_QL OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Profiles (Second Edition)

OWL 2 EL is particularly useful in applications employing ontologies that contain large numbers of properties and/or classes. This profile captures the expressive power used by many such ontologies and is a subset of OWL 2 for which the basic reasoning problems can be performed in time that is polynomial with respect to the size of the. Dedicated reasoning algorithms for this profile are available and have been demonstrated to be implementable in a highly scalable way.

4.2.2. RDF (Resource Description Framework)

RDF is a framework for Web information representation. It is a structured, graph-based model that enables interoperability and data exchange between systems, applications, and organizations by providing a shared understanding of a particular domain. In an RDF semantic ontology, information is represented as triples, which consist of a *subject*, *predicate*, and *object*. The subject is typically a resource, while the predicate describes a relationship between resources, and the object is either another resource or a literal value. RDF exploits classes and properties to define concepts and their relationships, respectively. The standardized way of representing knowledge that RDF bears, can be shared, and reused across different applications and domains. They can be used for various purposes, such as data integration, knowledge management, and semantic search. Furthermore, they provide a foundation for the development of more advanced semantic technologies, such as ontologies that include rules or entailment mechanisms for inferencing.

Primarily, RDF design intends to have simple data models, use formal semantics and provable inference, use XML-based syntax supporting schema datatypes and allowing anyone to make statements about the resource.

5. DATA CELLAR Ontology Development Methodology

The development of the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology is progressed according to the LOT principles, while METHONTOLOGY elements are exploited to enhance the development process where relevant.

The intention is to create the DATA CELLAR ontology by constructing a network of ontologies or modules that are interconnected through shared concepts and relationships. Each domain is constructed according to the process depicted in Figure 3, which identifies the actors/users participating in each step, the activities, and the resulting outputs based on the schema indicated by LOT.

Figure 3: Overview of the ontology development steps by LOT methodology

The methodology of Figure 3 delineates a series of sub-activities and their corresponding technological systems that can facilitate the execution of each activity. A comprehensive breakdown of each activity is expounded upon in subsequent sub-sections to provide a more detailed understanding.

The *Actors'* layer of Figure 3 indicates the individuals influencing the ontology development process. They are aligned above each *Activity* and *Output* of each step.

- *Ontology Developer*: An ontology developer is knowledgeable in ontology development and knowledge representation and is a member of the team working on ontology development.
- *Experts*: The experts in the domains addressed by the ontology, who are not required to possess knowledge associated with ontology development.
- *Users*: Refers to the end users that are going to potentially exploit the ontology directly rather than embedded in broader systems

5.1.1. Ontology requirements specification

The goal of ontology requirements specification activity is **to state “why” the ontology is being built, “what” its intended uses are, “who” the end-users are, and “which” requirements the ontology should fulfill.**

Therefore, the primary objective of this process is to articulate the underlying motives driving the development of the ontology, while also pinpointing and defining the specific criteria that the ontology should satisfy. To achieve this end, the active engagement and steadfast commitment of subject matter experts are indispensable to ensure that the final ontology accurately reflects the pertinent perspective and knowledge.

Within the context of DATA CELLAR, a top-down methodology development approach is employed, since at the current stage of project lifetime, the datasets stemming from the DATA CELLAR Validation Cases (VCs) are not available⁴⁸, however, the data categories are considered in line with the EU databases data categories assessed in Section 0 and the D2.1 indications. This approach aims at establishing the overall scope of the ontology, and to elicit the key requirements and constraints that guide its development. **The top-down method utilized in this context followed a rigorous process, which first defines the high-level domains and concepts that are relevant to the ontology, and then refines these concepts and their relationships to create a more detailed, and complete ontology.** The refinement is conducted regarding this approach, the ontology developers can ensure that the ontology is well-aligned with the requirements and constraints of the domain, and that it is possible to capture the most important and relevant aspects of the data once it becomes available.

The initial steps for developing an ontology with the top-down approach determine the key areas of focus and the corresponding information that need to be shared. These areas are derived from the feedback obtained from potential users of the DATA CELLAR system, which are gathered through a self-assessment tool development participatory approach as part of D1.1 - “DATA CELLAR potential users’ wishes and needs collected via a participatory approach also for LEC”.

Figure 4 illustrates the process for specifying requirements in the development of the DATA CELLAR ontology by the LOT methodology. The domains of knowledge are discerned and primarily cultivated in accordance with the proposed VCs, with an emphasis on the conditions surrounding the exchange of data. The LOT methodology provides targeted guidance for addressing these conditions through the “*Validation Case Specification*” and “*Purpose and Scope Identification*” activities, which are integrated with the project lifecycle and informed by the data sharing requirements articulated by the project consortium in D1.1.

⁴⁸ F.J. Lopez-Pellicer, L.M. Vilches-Blazquez, J. Norgueras-Iso, O. Corcho, M.A. Bernabe, A.F Rodriguez. (2007) “Using a hybrid approach for the development of an ontology in the hydrographical domain”.

Figure 4: Workflow diagram of ontology requirements specification (LOT)

The workflow of the ontology development in the top-down approach involves the indication of the domains and extraction of requirements of the project lifecycle. In this context, implementing development principles of METHONTOLOGY facilitates the process. Via answering relevant **competency questions** such as the ones referred earlier, (i) why this ontology is developed, (ii) what its intended uses and (iii) end-users are, etc. the scope and purpose of the ontology are indicated, and the *filling card* for the ontology requirements specification can be filled⁴⁹.

Following the Competency Questions, the ontology development team generates a **proposal for the ontology requirements**, to be complemented by domain experts and users.

Consequently, the **ontology requirements completion** is addressed by verifying the proposed requirements by the competency questions via comprehensive discussion during the bi-weekly T3.1 progress meetings with the relevant consortium members. Consortium partners contributed to the development and finalization of the functional ontology requirements proposal through providing lists with specific-domain-related data classification hierarchy (taxonomies) proposals, relevant properties, and metadata.

The **ORSD formalization** step addressed the filling card of the ontology which is presented in Table 1, concentrating the ontological requirements by answering the competency questions. The filling card offers a practical and simple explanation of the information involved in the activity. It also constitutes the output of the ontology requirements specification activity and is addressed as **Ontology Requirement Specification Document (ORSD)**.

Table 1: DATA CELLAR ORSD slots 1 to 6

Ontology Requirements Specification Document	
1	Purpose
	The purpose of building the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology is to provide a consensual knowledge model of the energy domain that can be used by LECs and through the other EU databases/dataspaces.

⁴⁹ Gómez-Pérez, A., Suárez-Figueroa, M.C.: NeOn Methodology: Scenarios for Building Networks of Ontologies. In: 16th International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management Knowledge Patterns (EKAW 2008). Conference Poster, Italy (2008)

2	Scope
	The scope of the ontologies is limited to the data shared and external data sources needed in the energy efficiency domain and related domains such as: (i) weather data, (ii) smart devices, (iii) energy generation technologies and sources, (iv) energy transmission and distribution, (v) energy market structures, (vi) energy consumption, (vii) energy storage, (viii) energy regulations, (ix) policies and standards, (x) efficiency, (xi) conservation practices and (xii) flexibility. The level of granularity is directly connected with the competency questions and terms identified.
3	Implementation Language
	The DATA CELLAR ontology is developed in the Ontology Web Language (OWL3), particularly the RDF.
4	Intended End-Users
User 1:	DATA CELLAR dataspace users – including the ones named in Section 0.
User 2:	DATA CELLAR platform end-users – including LEC operators, managers, stakeholders, decision makers, DSOs, TSOs, etc.
5	Intended Uses
Use 1:	Integration of external data sources - including sister projects' datasets (in diverse formats, e.g., xml, databases, text, etc.), and VC historic and near-real time data later.
Use 2:	Provide input for the DATA CELLAR data model development.
6	Ontology Requirements
a. Non-Functional Requirements	
NFR1:	• The ontology must support the English language.
NFR2:	• The ontology must be based on the European standards in existence or under development.
NFR3:	• The ontology must be modular.
NFR4:	• The ontology must have an open license and be publicly accessible online. However, the completeness of the ontology will be further developed in project subsequent tasks.
b. Functional Requirements: Group of Competency Questions	
CQ1:	What is the Energy Community location in the EU?
CQ2:	What are the different weather data?
CQ3:	What are the different types of energy generation technologies and RES?
CQ4:	What is the different energy transmission (TSO) and distribution (DSO) system description?
CQ5:	What is the energy market structure and the pricing?
CQ6:	What is the energy consumption, and usage patterns linked with the energy sources?
CQ7:	What are the systems and technologies for energy storage?
CQ8:	Which are the relevant regulations, policies, and standards?
CQ9:	What are energy efficiency and conservation practices and technologies?
CQ10:	What is the smart devices operation domain?

5.1.1.1. Structure of ontological requirements specification

During this phase, the primary platform utilized is the DATA CELLAR SharePoint, which is specifically designed for the DATA CELLAR consortium seamless interaction. DATA CELLAR SharePoint serves as a collaborative environment for organizing various aspects of projects, allowing every partner involved to share pertinent information with other teams. Within SharePoint, it is possible to create distinct sections for storing requirements related to DATA CELLAR metadata, dataspace, and ontologies. In addition, the regular T3.1-reposables meetings facilitated the development of the DATA CELLAR ORSD.

5.1.2. Ontology implementation

The ontology implementation process objective is to construct the ontology using a formal language, based on the ontological requirements identified. While modifications or additions to the requirements are permitted during the development, the initial set of requirements is defined before commencing the ontology implementation phase.

The implementation phase is carried out through multiple sprints, with the ontology developers scheduling and planning the development based on the prioritization of requirements in the ontology requirements specification process. The energy domain ontology is designed iteratively by the development team, with each repetition implementing only a limited number of requirements, while each repetition provides a new version of the ontology.

LOT methodology indicates the deviation of the ontology implementation activity depicted in Figure 5. The conceptualization, encoding, evaluation and reuse of ontology.

Figure 5: Workflow diagram of ontology implementation (LOT)

The models that are produced serve as a catalyst for the implementation of the ontology. This involves the formalization and completion of the design using implementation language. Ontology implementation activity demonstrates a series of sub-activities.

Initially, the knowledge domain of ontology must be specified. Thus, **Ontology Conceptualization** takes over to assemble an ontology model considering the requirements identified in the previous

section. The conceptualization includes specific constraints imposed from a formal language (not including complete terminology associated with the domain). The conceptualization identifies:

- The **ontology classes** which represent entities with common features, representing entities of the domain.
- The **class hierarchy** which indicates the subclasses of classes. In this element, a class A is a subclass of class B if and only if every instance of A is also an instance of B ($A \subseteq B$).
- The **ontology properties** which provide the relationship of an entity instance to some literal datatype value.
- A table with the available **metadata** of the respective ontological sections.

The part of ontology conceptualization is conducted in Section 0, where the taxonomies, the properties, the class hierarchies, and the metadata associated with DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology are demonstrated in simple table depictions.

The ontology is then produced in the implementation language, which is RDF⁵⁰ in the case of DATA CELLAR. **Ontology Encoding** bears also the classes, properties, axioms, and metadata developed in the previous step of conceptualization. Ontology editors are used by the developers to introduce the ontology elements in the implementation language. Ontology encoding into the **RDF framework** is conducted automatically, or semi-automatically via the ontology development platform used, the PROTÉGÉ⁵¹. Section 0, presents the conceptualized ontology incorporated into the ontology development platform, to produce the encoded version. The encoding also implies the techniques of migrating data from sources of different formats, as indicated in Section 6.1.4.

The capacity of reusability of ontology is investigated. During the activity step of **Ontology Reusability**, existing ontological modules, and/or complete existing ontologies, are evaluated in accordance with the DATA CELLAR requirements for potential reuse. The competency questions and/or the data are used to extract terminology for the domain. These terms are used during the ontology search with the aim of looking for existing ontologies that best fit DATA CELLAR ontology. The reused ontologies are commonly exploited during the conceptualization step of implementation. Section 0 shows an assortment of the existing ontologies that are considered during the DATA CELLAR ontology development. Reusing content manages to provide saving of costs and tools applying for other existing ontologies, together with the current one.

The ontology undergoes an initial **Ontology Evaluation** stage, which involves scrutiny of its various aspects. This evaluation is a vital step in ensuring the ontology's robustness and efficiency in serving its intended purpose. The evaluation seeks to identify and rectify any syntactic, modeling, or semantic errors that may impede the ontology's functionality. Moreover, it aims to verify the ontology's compliance with the data exchange requirements set for it, as outlined in the requirements specification process.

The evaluation stage under D3.1 involves an initial assessment since the ontology is not published online before the deliverable's finalization. The online publication requires the completion of data model and a more finalized status of interoperability.

⁵⁰ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁵¹ <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

5.1.2.1. Structure for ontology implementation

To facilitate the implementation of the energy domain ontology, a variety of specialized tools are employed by the developers aiming at editing, storing, and evaluating the ontology. During the conceptualization phase, the taxonomies and the properties are demonstrated in table formats, initially depicting the intricate relationships between the various concepts. Section 0, presents the conceptualized ontology incorporated into the ontology development platform, to produce the encoded version.

Regarding encoding step of the ontology, the PROTÉGÉ editor is exclusively used, contemplating empowerment for efficient generation of the ontology code while enabling the creation, visualization, and manipulation of ontologies in various representation formats, including knowledge graphs.

Furthermore, PROTÉGÉ is exploited in D3.1 for conducting the initial reasoning functionality. The reasoner is responsible for inferring logical consequences and evaluating the consistency and coherence of the ontology based on the defined axioms, rules, and constraints. It helps identify logical inconsistencies, implied relationships, and other inferences within the ontology. The PROTÉGÉ fixed reasoner (Hermit 1.4.3.456) did not provide any negative indication to all the ontologies, thus defining them *satisfiable*.

5.1.3. Ontology publication

Ontology publication involves creating a formal ontology that represents the relevant concepts and relationships within a particular domain of interest, and then publishing this ontology in a machine-readable format, such as **RDF/XML** in the DATA CELLAR case. Once published, the ontology can be used by other systems and applications to facilitate data integration, interoperability, and knowledge sharing within the LOT framework.

Figure 6: Workflow diagram of ontology publication (LOT)

The primary objective of the ontology publication process is to furnish an online ontology that can be accessed by humans in the form of a readable documentation and by machines as a file via its **Unique Resource Identifier (URI)**. Prior to its publication, the ontology must undergo evaluation to ensure that it is prepared for use.

The process of creating ontology documentation for a **Release Candidate** involves a collaborative effort between the ontology development team and domain experts. This documentation comprises an **HTML description** of the ontology, which details the ontology's classes, and properties. To accurately describe these, the domain experts work closely with the ontology development team. The documentation also includes metadata, such as date of creation, last modification, and description.

The ontology development team, in close collaboration with domain experts, proceeds with the generation of the **Ontology Documentation**. This process involves considering the ontology code generated in the HTML activities, as well as a comprehensive review of the ontology structure, concepts, and relationships. The ontology documentation aims to provide a detailed description of the ontology's purpose, scope, and applicability. It also includes information on the ontology's syntax, semantics, and modeling principles, as well as instructions on how to use and interpret the ontology. The documentation is considered an essential artifact of the ontology development process, as it provides a clear and comprehensive understanding of the ontology, enabling effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders. The ontology documentation is an essential component of the release candidate, ensuring that the ontology is well-documented, reliable, and easily maintainable over time.

The ontology development process requires creating an HTML description that provides an overview of the ontology's structure, *including classes, properties, and data properties*. Collaborative efforts between domain experts and the ontology development team ensure accurate descriptions, and metadata captures essential information such as creator, publisher, and version number.

Diagrams are created to store the graphical representation of the ontology, which includes taxonomy and class diagrams. These diagrams serve as a visual representation of the ontology's structure, making it easier to understand and communicate its core concepts and relationships. In some cases, the ontology may be large and complex, requiring the use of diagrams to summarize top-level entities. These diagrams play a critical role in facilitating effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders, enabling them to quickly grasp the ontology's structure and identify potential areas for improvement or refinement.

The **Online Publication** implies the best practices for publishing vocabularies on the Web. The online ontology is accessible via its namespace URI as a machine-readable file and a human readable documentation using content negotiation. However, this step is expected to be fulfilled in later stages of the DATA CELLAR interoperability development, under WP3.

5.1.3.1. Structure for ontology publication

Under D3.1, the dissemination of the ontology is limited only in consortium-internal publication, executed through SharePoint. The ontology conceptualization is demonstrated in Section 0 for concept evaluation, while the HTMLs are included in the ANNEX. The PROTÉGÉ editor is exploited to produce the RDF scripts of the ontologies, and the knowledge graphs of the DATA CELLAR ontology that are presented in the ANNEX and in Section 0 respectively. In addition, the ontology documentations are produced by the PROTÉGÉ add-on of OWLDoc and are hosted in SharePoint too. These OWLDocs with the HTMLs will be later available for public access. Since the HTML links

are not publicly available, the relevant script is included in the ANNEX, together with an OWLDoc paradigm screenshot.

5.1.4. Ontology maintenance

The primary objective of **ontology maintenance** is to ensure that the ontology remains relevant, and up to date. This may necessitate updating the ontology in response to new demands, rectifying any errors, or initiating a fresh iteration of the ontology development process. During the ontology development stage, domain experts may recommend new requirements or enhancements to the ontology. Upon review and approval by the ontology development team, these recommendations are incorporated into the ontology. The workflow diagram of the ontology maintenance step is demonstrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Workflow diagram of ontology maintenance (LOT)

5.1.4.1. Structure for ontology maintenance

The ontology maintenance process is facilitated by an **issue tracker** seamlessly utilized by the ontology developers and the consortium members in general, to keep track of, and address any concerns or suggestions identified by domain experts and ontology developers. The maintenance step includes the development of a bug detector, which is going to be developed in the upcoming steps of DATA CELLAR when addressing the requirements for interoperability.

In order to ensure consistency and coherence, any modifications, or advancements to the ontology must be unanimously agreed upon by the entire ontology development team. The ontology development team conducts bi-weekly meetings communicating the potential existing issues, while leveraging the project’s SharePoint platform to host an excel as an issue tracker mechanism, to deliberate on enhancements and problems pertaining to domains and taxonomies.

Figure 8: Issue Tracker available in the SharePoint

Figure 8 presents a screenshot of the Issue Tracker attributed to the ontology development process, which is accessible by all responsible for the ontology partners. Figure 9 shows a part of the issues section associated with DATA CELLAR ontology.

Issue Tracker					
No.	Open Issues	Issuer	Assignee	Issue Comment	Status Mark
1	T1.1 link with the ontology data	EDP	UBE	no com	Closed
2	Develop Taxonomies for the Smart Device Class	UBE	EDF	no com	Closed
3	Develop Taxonomies for the Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems	UBE	EPL	no com	Closed

Figure 9: Issues Tracker screenshot related to DATA CELLAR ontology

Should domain experts, or ontology developers propose the inclusion of novel concepts in the ontology, they must present their recommendations in each team meeting and generate a new issue in the SharePoint issue tracker, which will be used as the foundation for initiating a comprehensive discussion on the feasibility and approval of the proposal.

SharePoint issues are marked as “open” and “closed”. The issues can also have an assignee, which is the person that is responsible for moving the issue forward.

This deliverable presents an advanced and meticulously designed methodology for conceptual analysis through ontologies. Its primary objective is to enhance clarity regarding modelling assumptions for T4.1 while generating robust and well-structured taxonomies.

6. Ontologies Reuse in DATA CELLAR

Ontologies are classification systems specifying entities, definitions and inter-relationships for a given domain⁵². Developing Local Energy Communities (LEC) is a multidisciplinary research activity since engineering, economics, and meteorology experts often work together. A common vocabulary that described the players (human beings and devices) and their possible interactions is mandatory to properly interact. Moreover, if well-designed, already existing ontologies can be reused, increasing the integration and interoperability of different systems.

This chapter briefly describes the existing ontologies that have been reused to implement the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology, under the *LOT - implementation step*.

6.1. Assessment of Existing Ontologies to be Reused in the DATA CELLAR Ontology

The ontologies reused by the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology are primarily in confines of their principle and their approach on addressing the relevant topics. The core ontologies reused for the DATA CELLAR ontology are:

6.1.1. SAREF

Smart Applications REFERENCE ontology (SAREF) is based on the “device” concept, which is defined as a tangible object designed to accomplish a particular task. Each device executes one or more functions to accomplish the task for which it was installed in households, common public buildings, or offices. SAREF ontology is modular, allowing the definition of any device from pre-defined building blocks, based on the function(s) that the device performs. The functions are represented through a dedicated class (saref:Function), with at least one associated command.

Moreover, a device can be characterized by a profile, which is the specification associated with a device to collect information about a certain property or commodity (e.g., energy, or water) for optimizing its usage in the home/building in which the device is located. Finally, the classes saref:Measurement, saref:Property and saref:UnitOfMeasure allow to relate different measurements from a given device for different properties measured in different units⁵³.

In the context of DATA CELLAR, particular classification methods and principles are attributed to the SAREF ontology. DATA CELLAR does not leverage solid components from SAREF, but the initial approach on classifying smart devices.

6.1.2. ThinkHome

ThinkHome ontology aims to create a comprehensive knowledge base to develop energy-efficient and intelligent control mechanisms⁵⁴. Introducing semantic context and artificial intelligence,

⁵² Norris, E., Finnerty, A. N., Hastings, J., Stokes, G., & Michie, S. (2019). A scoping review of ontologies related to human behaviour change. *Nature human behaviour*, 3(2), 164-172.

⁵³ SAREF: the Smart Applications REFERENCE ontology (etsi.org) - <https://saref.etsi.org/core/v3.1.1/>

⁵⁴ Reinisch, C., Kofler, M., Iglesias, F., & Kastner, W. (2011). Thinkhome energy efficiency in future smart homes. *EURASIP Journal on Embedded Systems*, 2011, 1-18.

ThinkHome contributes to the design of the future smart home through embedded control strategies that cooperate within the highly interoperable ThinkHome system structure. This system provides different services, such as transparent access to data, users and building systems. Two main objectives are persecuted: energy efficiency and comfort. It can be seen as a digital ecosystem due to its collaborative characteristic, where advanced methods and algorithms are applied to optimize control decisions and dedicated parts to facilitate information availability and access.

ThinkHome is developed using the Web Ontology Language (OWL) and is based on three pillars: concepts, properties, and individuals:

- Concepts define general ideas of a possible item in the defined knowledge base. Organizing the identified concepts in a subsumption hierarchy, which means in a super-class/sub-class connection, is recommended.
- Properties are the relations between concepts and are grouped into two categories. Object properties establish connections between different concepts. Datatype properties connect concepts with values of a specified datatype.
- Individuals are distinct from the conceptual model and act as concrete instantiations.

The DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology valorises the ThinkHome ontology in the boundaries of “Energy efficiency technologies” domain.

6.1.3. OEMA

Ontology for Energy Management Applications (OEMA) aims to represent all the main energy data domains, such as infrastructure technical details, energy consumptions, performance, and contextual data⁵⁵. This ontology wants to unify already existing heterogeneous ontologies, providing a common representation of energy data. OEMA is an ontology network, formed by 6 interconnected domain ontologies, interconnected through ThinkHome ontology that has been selected due to its modular approach and completeness. Even if ThinkHome was originally designed within the “home” framework, it can be easily adapted to other contexts such as microgrid energy management.

The OEMA infrastructure ontology contains several data types:

- Infrastructures/Building types (e.g., household, microgrid)
- Technical data (e.g., material, surface)
- Space data (e.g., floors, rooms)
- Geometrical data (e.g., floor area)

The OEMA ontology network non-functional requirements cover the following aspects in regard of DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology:

- Represented energy domains are classified into different sub-ontologies or modules, which are known as domain ontologies (Table 2). This modularized structure facilitates ontology reuse and modification when adapting it to different energy management scenarios.
- Each ontology element (class, property) must be named using only one term to avoid semantic heterogeneity.

⁵⁵ Corrado, V., Ballarini, I., Madrazo, L., & Nemirovskij, G. (2015). *Data structuring for the ontological modelling of urban energy systems: The experience of the SEMANCO project. Sustainable Cities and Society, 14*, 223-235.

Table 2: OEMA sub-ontologies

Sub-ontology name	Sub-ontology objects, concepts, data, device
Energy and equipment ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ energy equipment - building automation system resources (sensors, actuators/controllers, HVAC) ○ industrial equipment (i.e., construction and manufacturing equipment) ○ energy generators (e.g., EVs, Home Power Plants) ○ power storage/energy carriers
Geographical ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ geographical data about infrastructures ○ energy equipment locations (city, district, etc. / mountain, sea, etc. / altitude, depth)
External factors ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ climate type (e.g., alpine, continental) ○ environmental conditions (e.g., lighting, noise) ○ weather phenomenon (e.g., temperature)
Energy saving ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ general energy saving recommendations. ○ personalized energy saving recommendations
Smart Grid stakeholders' ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ smart Grid stakeholders and roles in the energy market (e.g., energy consumers, energy suppliers, Distribution System Operators) ○ energy flexibility operations, (e.g., market processes, flex-offers exchange)
Units ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ energy units, ○ area units, ○ capacity units , ○ currency

6.1.4. OEO

The Open Energy Ontology (OEO) is a domain ontology of the energy system analysis context⁵⁶. It is developed as part of the Open Energy Family through the Manchester OWL Syntax. It is designed to improve transparency and facilitate comparability and transferability of energy system modelling and scenario analysis. It is organized into 5 sub-ontologies, which are described in Table 3.

Table 3: OEO sub-ontologies

Sub-ontology name	Sub-ontology objects, concepts, data, device
Geography	Location of energy generation, consumption, transmission
Meteorology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fluctuating renewable energy generation, ○ Extreme weather situations
Math / Computer sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Modeling methods
Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy and emission markets ○ Prices and costs ○ Socio-economic developments
Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Technologies ○ Efficiency ○ Future development

⁵⁶ Booshehri, M., Emele, L., Flügel, S., Förster, H., Frey, J., & Frey, U. (2021). *Introducing the open energy ontology: Enhancing data interpretation and interfacing in energy systems analysis. Energy and AI 2021; 5: 100074.*

DATA CELLAR considers a variety of the above sub-ontologies concerning the development of its core ontologies such as the energy efficiency, market, prices, etc.

6.1.5. SEMANCO

Semantic Tools for Carbon Reduction in Urban Planning (SEMANCO) project aims to develop an ontology-based energy information system and associated tools to support urban planners in reducing CO₂ emissions in cities⁵⁷. According to the proposed methodology, ontologies are developed from the requirement analysis performed at the case studies. In this way, data, services, and stakeholders can be included in the process of building ontologies. To create the ontology-based system, a decentralized approach was adopted. A semantic framework links ontology that are related to different domains. The urban scale design and the integration of GIS with linked data makes SEMANCO particularly interest in developing LEC.

The formal ontology is developed with OWL 2 (Web Ontology Language 2). SEMANCO is based on the integration of energy-related open data structured according to standards, semantically modelled and interoperable with toolsets. It comprises a multitude of diverse source concepts, such as standards, use cases, activity descriptions, and data sources related to energy management and urban planning domains. Moreover, several attributes are defined to characterize regions, cities, neighborhoods, buildings, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, climate and socio-economic factors influencing energy consumption.

The tools provided by SEMANCO allow us to visualize, simulate and analyze the multiple relationships between factors determining CO₂ production.

⁵⁷ Corrado, V., Ballarini, I., Madrazo, L., & Nemirovskij, G. (2015). Data structuring for the ontological modelling of urban energy systems: The experience of the SEMANCO project. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 14, 223-235.

7. Data Migration to Ontologies

This section outlines the procedure for converting data in different formats into an RDF graph that adheres to the DATA CELLAR ontology. This conversion is crucial to unify diverse data assets and add semantic annotations, enabling their effective utilization within the DATA CELLAR ecosystem. Although the existing data assets hold significant value, their usefulness is limited without an interoperable model like the DATA CELLAR ontology to connect them.

Figure 10 shows a diagram that illustrates the process defined in this section from a high-level point of view.

Figure 10: Data migration workflow

- The original data assets are sourced from various data sources, which can be in different formats such as **unstructured** data (e.g., plain text), **semi-structured** data (e.g., XML), and structured data from a **database**. Additionally, **UML class diagrams** are also integrated into the diagram and are discussed below.
- Two **parsers** are employed to extract data from the original data sources and convert it into an intermediate tabular data format. These parsers are necessary for handling unstructured

and semi-structured data sources. Although the database requires a software component to perform this transformation, it is relatively straightforward.

- The **intermediate tabular data format** serves as a stable in-memory representation of the data assets and provides a starting point for the *RDF mapper* to convert the data into an RDF graph.
- The **RDF mapper** is a custom software component responsible for reading the intermediate tabular data format, incorporating semantic annotations that align with the DATA CELLAR ontology, and generating an RDF graph that represents the original data within the DATA CELLAR framework.
- Lastly, it is advisable to store the resulting RDF graph in an **RDF triple store**, which is a specialized database designed for persisting and querying data contained in RDF graphs. Neo4J, the recommended graph database in this section, is not precisely an RDF triple store. Nevertheless, it serves the same purpose and can be seen as equivalent.

To successfully implement the data migration process, it is necessary to develop three distinct software modules as mentioned earlier. **This represents the main challenge for data migration** and requires a combination of domain-specific knowledge of the data assets, familiarity with the DATA CELLAR ontology, and software development skills.

- Among these modules, the **unstructured parser** poses the greatest complexity. Unstructured data lacks any predefined structure, making it difficult to establish a rules-based process for transforming the original data into a structured format. A thorough analysis of the unstructured data is necessary to identify potential patterns. The final implementation will likely involve heuristics that may not capture all relevant data in a tabular format.
- Assuming a sufficient understanding of the DATA CELLAR ontology and the RDF stack, developing the **RDF mapper** is a time-consuming task of medium-low complexity. The RDF mapper must incorporate the necessary logic to determine the mapping of ontology classes and properties to corresponding tables and their relationships.
- Lastly, the development of the **semi-structured parser** is a relatively straightforward task. It primarily requires knowledge of the schema of the semi-structured data source, which can be obtained during an initial exploratory phase.

Below is a suggested technology stack that can be utilized for the implementation of the data migration process from end to end:

- In this case, it is recommended to use **Python** as the programming language. This choice is primarily based on the wide availability of software libraries and tools, as well as its relatively low barrier of entry.

- Among the software libraries for working with the RDF technology stack, **rdflib**⁵⁸ stands out. By leveraging rdflib, the developer gains access to comprehensive functionalities for handling RDF graphs and interacting with various RDF serialization formats (e.g., RDF/XML, Turtle). It's worth noting that rdflib is implemented in Python.
- **Neo4J**⁵⁹ serves as a specialized graph database designed to handle data in the form of graphs, as opposed to traditional tables in relational databases. **Neosemantics**⁶⁰, an extension of Neo4J, enhances its capabilities by enabling the understanding of RDF triples. This integration allows Neo4J to leverage all its powerful features within an RDF graph. The combination of Neo4J and Neosemantics offers a valuable solution for long-term persistence of RDF datasets. Furthermore, it facilitates real-time querying of these datasets with excellent performance, supporting a wide range of programming languages.
- **Pandas**⁶¹ is another key library in the Python ecosystem. Its core concept revolves around the DataFrame entity, which is especially suitable for representing tabular data. Pandas could prove to be a good choice for the intermediate tabular data format. One remarkable advantage of Pandas is its built-in functionality for reading relational databases and semi-structured formats directly into a DataFrame. This would greatly reduce the complexity of the implementation of the parsers.
- **UML class diagrams** can be considered distinct from semi-structured, unstructured, and database data sources. They offer a structured representation of the data model's entities and their interconnections. Some might argue that UML class diagrams convey information comparable to an ontology, although UML class diagrams are primarily geared towards aiding software development, whereas OWL-based ontologies enable sophisticated reasoning and inference. In the DATA CELLAR project's data migration context, UML class diagrams would provide precise details about the intermediate data structure's tables (i.e., Pandas DataFrames), columns, and the relationships among these tables.

58 <https://rdflib.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

59 <https://neo4j.com/docs/>

60 <https://neo4j.com/labs/neosemantics/>

61 <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

8. DATA CELLAR Ontology Conceptualization

This Section presents the concepts of DATA CELLAR classification, including the taxonomies, and the properties. The axioms are well defined via the interactions of the classes and properties, e.g., classes, subclasses, and properties concerning the relevant classes and subclasses. The conceptualization section constitutes the initial input for the PROTÉGÉ encoding in the following Section 0. In addition, an indication regarding the knowledge domain that is exploited in the context of the D3.1 is demonstrated.

8.1. Domain Specific of Knowledge

Domain-specific ontologies serve as means to define the ontological agreements and commitments between information providers and users within an information infrastructure. They leverage domain-specific knowledge to address the challenges posed by the overwhelming amount of information available. This is accomplished through two key approaches: (i) *Reusing and organizing knowledge from existing real-world ontologies*: This involves mapping semantic concepts from ontologies to data structures in underlying repositories. By doing so, knowledge can be efficiently reused and organized, enabling effective information management. (ii) *Integrating and developing mechanisms for translating information requests across ontologies*: This entails creating methods and tools to bridge the gap between different ontologies and facilitate the exchange of information. By enabling seamless communication across ontologies, the integration and translation of knowledge becomes possible, improving the overall interoperability and effectiveness of information retrieval processes⁶².

The goal of domain-specific ontology is to create a structured representation of knowledge in a particular domain that is accurate, complete, and consistent. This can be used to support a wide range of applications, such as information retrieval, data integration, semantic search, and knowledge management. The domain of knowledge is addressed by answering the CQ indicated in the first stage of LOT, in Table 1.

8.2. Taxonomy structure, categories, and sub-categories

In this section, we are presented with an overview of the terminologies employed within the context of the D3.1 work, which is expected to serve as a foundational reference for the development of the data model definition in *D4.1 - "DATA CELLAR Overall platform reference architecture and Data Model Definition"*. The definitions and terminologies presented in this section serve as a means of establishing a common understanding of the technical concepts and terms that are expected to be utilized throughout the project. This exercise enhances the precision and clarity of the results, thereby fostering effective communication and a shared understanding among stakeholders.

8.3. DATA CELLAR Ontologies

Regarding the ontology conceptualization under the Ontology Implementation step, DATA CELLAR initially developed the classification taxonomies and properties, in accordance with the EU databases

⁶² N. Guarino – *Formal Ontology in Information Systems (1998)*, E. Mena, V. Kashyap, A. Illarramendi, A. Steth, - *Domain Specific Ontologies for Semantic Information Brokering on the Global Information Infrastructure*

of Section 0, while highly considering the reuse of the existing ontologies researched in Section 0. The current section demonstrates the conceptual approach of the DATA CELLAR ontologies designed drafted with simplicity in doc. format.

8.3.1. DATA CELLAR ontology conceptualization

The DATA CELLAR ontological categories are presented separately and in sub-sections based on their higher-class level. The properties are also included together with the taxonomies.

The following sub-sections unveil the ontological categories within the realm of DATA CELLAR. This deliverable serves as an exemplar of a comprehensive and refined conceptualization stage of ontology. The ontological conceptualization is hosted in SharePoint and is accessible to the consortium partners for comments, feedback, and evaluation. The complete demonstration of conceptualization is avoided, since the step of **LOT methodology - Implementation Objective**, involving encoding, bears the HTML descriptions of the taxonomies and properties, which together with their RDFs are presented in the ANNEX.

Therefore, the ontological categories addressed by the DATA CELLAR are namely:

1. Energy market structures and pricing;
2. Energy regulations, policies, and standards;
3. Energy efficiency technologies;
4. Energy generation technologies and sources;
5. Energy transmission and distribution systems;
6. Energy consumption and usage patterns;
7. Energy storage systems and technologies;
8. Smart Devices.

The subsequent sub-sections exemplify the comprehensive conceptualization of the ontologies, encompassing essential elements such as metadata, taxonomies, and properties. As the DATA CELLAR ontology is not currently publicly accessible, D3.1 serves to showcase the ontologies' conceptual stage, highlighting their development and structure.

8.3.1.1. Energy market structures and pricing Conceptualization

Table 4: Conceptualization of Energy market structures and pricing ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Market_and_Pricing
Description	The Energy market structures and pricing taxonomy is a comprehensive classification of the different types of wholesale and retail energy markets, pricing models, and regulatory structures. The wholesale energy markets are categorized into different market types such as spot, forward, futures, options, and day-ahead markets, each with its own market mechanisms like auctions, bilateral contracts, and power purchase agreements. The taxonomy also covers the market participants , including suppliers, consumers, brokers, aggregators, and independent system operators. Regulatory structures are further classified as either deregulated or regulated markets, and market power mitigation measures and anti-trust laws are also considered. Retail energy markets are categorized based on the types of customers, including residential, commercial, industrial, and

	government and institutional. Finally, the pricing models are classified as cost-based, marginal cost, average cost, time-of-use, real-time, and inclining block rates, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. This sophisticated taxonomy provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex and dynamic world of energy markets and pricing.
Scope	This taxonomy enhances understanding of the dynamic energy market landscape.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string

Table 5: Energy Market and Pricing Conceptual Taxonomy
Market Structure

- Wholesale Energy Markets
 - Market Types
 - Spot Markets
 - Forward Markets
 - Futures Markets
 - Options Markets
 - Day-Ahead Markets
 - Market Mechanisms
 - Auctions
 - Bilateral Contracts
 - Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)
 - Net Metering
 - Feed-in Tariffs (FITs)
 - Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS)
 - Market Participants
 - Suppliers
 - Consumers
 - Brokers
 - Aggregators
 - Independent System Operators (ISOs)
 - Regulatory Structures
 - Deregulated Markets
 - Regulated Markets
 - Market Power Mitigation
 - Anti-Trust Laws
- Retail-Energy Markets
 - Residential
 - Commercial
 - Industrial
 - Government and Institutional
- Pricing Model
 - Cost-based Pricing
 - Marginal Cost Pricing
 - Average Cost Pricing

- Time-of-Use Pricing
- Real-Time Pricing
- Inclining Block Rates

Energy Market and Pricing Conceptual Properties

- hasMarketMechanism
- hasMarketParticipants
- hasMarketType
- hasPricingModel
- hasRegulatoryStructures
- hasRetailEnergyMarkets

8.3.1.2. Energy regulations, policies, and standards Conceptualization

Table 6: Conceptualization of Energy Regulations, Policies, and Standards ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Regulations_Policies_Standards
Description	The Energy Regulations, Policies, and Standards ontology provides a comprehensive framework for classifying and organizing the various policy and regulatory bodies, policy types, instruments, and market regulations related to the energy sector. The ontology includes a range of policy and regulatory bodies, such as national energy regulators, international energy agencies, and government energy ministries. It also covers different types of energy policies, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, climate change mitigation, energy security, and sustainable development. The energy policy instruments identified in the ontology include feed-in tariffs, net metering, tax incentives, carbon pricing, renewable portfolio standards, energy efficiency standards, and building codes and standards. Additionally, the ontology encompasses international energy agreements and standards, such as the Paris Agreement, Kyoto Protocol, and ISO-energy management standards. Finally, the ontology provides a detailed classification of energy market regulations, including electricity market regulations and oil and gas industry regulations. By providing a comprehensive framework for organizing and classifying the various energy policies, regulations, and standards, the Energy Regulations, Policies, and Standards ontology can help policymakers, regulators, and other stakeholders better understand the complex and evolving energy landscape.
Scope	A comprehensive framework for classifying policy bodies, types, instruments, and market regulations in the energy sector, including national regulators, policy types (renewable energy, energy efficiency), instruments (feed-in tariffs, carbon pricing), international agreements (Paris Agreement), and market regulations (electricity, oil, and gas).
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX

Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string
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Table 7: Energy Regulations Policies and Standards Conceptual Taxonomy

Energy regulations policies standards

- Policy and Regulatory Bodies
 - National Energy Regulators
 - Member States Authorities
 - International Energy Agencies
 - IEA
 - IRENA
 - OACED
 - REN21
 - Government Energy Ministries
 - Member States Ministries
 - Environmental Protection Agencies
 - Public Utilities Commissions
 - Other Relevant Government Departments
- Energy Policy Types
 - Renewable Energy
 - Energy Efficiency
 - Climate Change Mitigation
 - Energy Security
 - Sustainable Development
- Energy Policy Instruments
 - Feed-In Tariffs (FITs)
 - Net-Metering
 - Tax Incentives
 - Carbon Pricing
 - Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS)
 - Energy Efficiency Standards
 - Energy Performance Certificates
 - Building Codes&Standards
 - Appliance&Equipment Efficiency Standards
- International Energy Agreements&Standards
 - Paris Agreement
 - Kyoto Protocol
 - IECC
 - ISO energy management standards
 - IEC energy standards
- Energy Market Regulations
 - Electricity Market Regulations
 - Market Design
 - Transmission&Distribution System
 - Retail Competition
 - Market Monitoring&Enforcement
 - Renewable Energy Integration
 - Oil&Gas Industry Regulations
 - Exploration&Production
 - Transportation&Storage
 - Refining&Distribution

- Environmental
- Safety

Energy Regulations Policies and Standards Conceptual Properties

- Agreements_&_Standards
- hasPolicyBody
- hasPolicyInstruments
- hasRegulations
- hasType
- IsInternationalAgency

8.3.1.3. Energy efficiency technologies Conceptualization

Table 8: Conceptualization of Energy efficiency technologies ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Efficiency_Technologies
Description	The implementation of energy-efficient technologies is crucial for reducing energy consumption, improving sustainability, and minimizing environmental impact. This section covers a comprehensive ontology taxonomy of energy-efficient technologies, including HVAC systems, lighting systems, building envelope systems, vapor barriers, insulation, and energy-efficient appliances and equipment . The HVAC systems are classified into central, packaged, window AC, portable AC, heat pump, and geothermal, while the lighting systems are categorized as incandescent, fluorescent, LED, and smart. Building envelope systems encompass roofing, walls, and openings, where the latter are further classified into window types, frames, and glazing, as well as door types and materials. Vapor barriers and insulation, on the other hand, are categorized based on their material, use case, and performance. Lastly, the section includes a classification of energy-efficient appliances and equipment, including refrigerators and freezers, dishwashers, clothes washers and dryers, air conditioners, furnaces and boilers, heat pumps, water heaters, and industrial process and manufacturing technologies such as material handling and storage, HVAC, automation, and control. By understanding these classifications, individuals can make informed decisions when selecting and implementing energy-efficient technologies to promote a sustainable and efficient future.
Scope	Understanding these classifications enables informed decision-making in selecting and implementing energy-efficient technologies for a sustainable future.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string, int, float

Table 9: Energy Efficient Technologies Conceptual Taxonomy
Energy efficient technologies

HVAC systems

- Central
- Packaged
- Window AC
- Portable AC
- Heat Pump
- Geothermal

Lighting systems

- Incandescent
- Fluorescent
- LED
- Smart

Building envelope systems

- Roof
 - Pitched roofing
 - Flat roofing
 - Green roofing
 - Solar roofing
- Walls
 - Masonry
 - Steel
 - Wood
 - Concrete
 - ICF (Insulated concrete forms)
- Openings
 - Window Types
 - Single Hung
 - Double Hung
 - Casement
 - Awning
 - Sliding
 - Skylights
 - Transom
 - Window Frames
 - Wood
 - Aluminum
 - Vinyl
 - Fiberglass
 - Window Glazing
 - Single Pane
 - Double Pane
 - Triple Pane
 - Low E-Coating
 - Gas Filled Windows
 - Tinted Windows
 - Door Types
 - Hinged
 - Sliding
 - Bi-Fold
 - Door Materials
 - Wood
 - Steel

- Fiberglass
 - Aluminum
- Vapor Barriers
- Insulation
 - Material based
 - Fiberglass
 - Mineral wool
 - Cellulose
 - Reflective
 - Radiant barrier
 - Aerogel
 - Polystyrene
 - Natural insulation (wool, cotton, straw, etc.)
 - Use case based
 - Attic insulation
 - Wall insulation
 - Floor insulation
 - Pipe insulation
 - Duct insulation
 - Performance based
 - High performance
 - Low VOC
 - Fire resistant
 - Soundproofing
 - Moisture resistant

Energy Efficient Appliances&Equipment

- Refrigerators&Freezers
- Dishwashers
- Clothes Washers
- Clothes Dryers
- Air Conditioners
- Furnaces&Boilers
- Heat Pumps
- Water Heaters

Industrial Process&Manufacturing Technologies

- Material Handling&Storage
- HVAC
- Automation&Control

Energy Efficient Technologies Conceptual Properties

- hasApplianceEquipment
- hasBuildingEnvelope
 - o hasInsulation
 - basedOn
 - o hasOpenings
 - o hasRoof
 - o hasVaporBarrier
 - o hasWalls
- hasHVAC
- hasLightingSystem
- IndustrialProcess

8.3.1.4. Energy conservation practices Conceptualization

Table 10: Conceptualization of Energy Conservation Practices ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Consvration_Practices
Description	Energy conservation practices are essential for reducing energy consumption and promoting sustainability. This ontology taxonomy provides a structured framework for understanding the different types of energy conservation practices. The first category is behavioural practices , which involve adopting energy-efficient habits, efficient use of energy-consuming devices, and conducting energy audits and assessments. The second category is building systems optimization , which includes optimizing HVAC systems, lighting systems, building envelopes, implementing water conservation measures, and installing renewable energy systems. The final category is transportation , which covers the use of fuel-efficient vehicles, electric vehicles, and public transportation. By implementing these energy conservation practices, individuals and organizations can significantly reduce their energy consumption and contribute to a more sustainable future.
Scope	This taxonomy promotes energy conservation and sustainability.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string, float

Table 11: Energy Conservation Practices Conceptual Taxonomy

Energy conservation practices

- Behavioural practices
 - Energy efficient habits
 - Efficient use of energy consuming devices
 - Energy audits&assessments
- Building systems optimization
 - HVAC optimization
 - Lighting optimization
 - Building envelope optimization
 - Water conservation measures
 - Renewable energy systems installation
- Transportation
 - Fuel efficient vehicles
 - EVs
 - Public transportation

Energy Conservation Conceptual Properties

- hasConsercationPractice
- hasPractices
- systemOptimization
- Transportation

8.3.1.5. Energy generation technologies and sources Conceptualization

Table 12: Conceptualization of Energy Generation Technologies and Sources ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Generation_Technologies_and_Sources
Description	The proposed classification taxonomy distinguishes between primary and secondary energy generation , where the former refers to the extraction of raw energy sources, while the latter pertains to the conversion of primary energy sources into usable forms. The primary energy generation category encompasses the use of fossil fuels, biomass, and renewable energy sources, while the secondary energy generation category includes electricity and heat generation, as well as combined heat and power systems. Furthermore, the taxonomy provides subcategories for each type of primary energy generation, including various types of fossil fuels and renewable energy sources, which facilitates a more granular analysis of energy production processes.
Scope	The taxonomy enables a detailed analysis of energy production processes.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: rational, string, float

Table 13: Energy Generation Conceptual Taxonomy

Energy-Generation

Primary Energy Generation

- Fossil Fuels
 - Coal
 - Oil
 - Natural-Gas
- Biomass
- Renewable Energy Sources
 - Solar Power
 - Wind Power
 - Hydro Power
 - Geothermal Power

Secondary Energy Generation

- Electricity Generation
- Heat Generation
- CHP (Combined Heat and Power systems)

Measurement

Unit of measurement

- Electricity Generation: kilowatt hour (kWh)
- Liquid Fuel: Tons oil equivalent (toe)
- Solid Fuel: Cubic meters (m³)

Energy Generation Conceptual Properties:

- hasEnergySource

- hasMeasurement
- hasSecondaryGeneration
- hasUnitOfMeasurement
- hasFuelType

8.3.1.6. Energy transmission and distribution systems Conceptualization

Table 14: Conceptualization of Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Transmission_Systems
Description	The Energy Transmission and Distribution System taxonomy is a comprehensive classification of the infrastructure that enables the distribution of energy from production facilities to consumers. This taxonomy includes properties such as location, operator, capacity, length, and start date, which provide important information about the system's physical and operational characteristics. Additionally, the taxonomy includes technologies used in energy transmission and distribution systems, as well as their purpose and the energy commodity being transported. For instance, the system can distribute renewable and non-renewable electricity , natural gas, and oil. The electrical grid subcategory includes the current type and voltage level, with alternative current (AC) and direct current (DC) being the main types and low, medium, and high voltage being the common voltage levels. Finally, the taxonomy includes a subcategory for pipeline systems, which describes their pressure levels, with low and high pressure being the primary options. This taxonomy offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the infrastructure required for energy transmission and distribution.
Scope	It provides a framework for understanding energy transmission and distribution infrastructure.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: rational, string, float

Table 15: Energy Transmission and Distribution System Conceptual Taxonomy
Energy-Transmission-Distribution-System

- Property
 - Location
 - Rural
 - Urban
 - Operator
 - Capacity
 - Length
 - StartDate
 - Technologies
 - Purpose
 - Energy-Commodity

- Electricity
 - Renewable-Electricity
 - Solar Electricity
 - Wind Electricity
 - Hydro Electricity
 - Bio Electricity
 - Non-Renewable-Electricity
 - Fossil-Fuel-Electricity
 - Coal Electricity
 - Oil Electricity
 - Natural Gas Electricity
- Natural Gas
- Oil
- Electrical-Grid
 - Current-Type
 - Alternative-Current_AC
 - Direct-Current_DC
 - Voltage-Level
 - Low-Voltage_LV
 - Medium-Voltage_MV
 - High-Voltage_HV
 - Pipeline-System
 - Pressure
 - Low
 - High

Properties:

- hasCapacity
- hasCurrentType
- hasElectricitySource
- hasElectricityType
- hasEnergyCommodity
- hasLength
- hasLocation
- hasOperator
- hasPipelineSystem
- hasTechnologies
- hasVoltageType

8.3.1.7. Energy consumption and usage patterns Conceptualization

Table 16: Conceptualization of Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Usage_Patterns
Description	Energy-Consumption-Pattern taxonomy used to classify the various aspects of energy consumption . This classification is based on several factors, including location, unit of measurement, value, and date and time. The taxonomy includes a classification of energy consumption by sector , such as residential, commercial, and industrial, as well as energy usage patterns, such as hourly, daily, weekly, and

	monthly. Energy sources are classified as renewable or non-renewable, with subcategories for solar, wind, hydro, and bioenergy sources, and fossil fuel sources like coal, oil, and natural gas. The usage type of the energy consumption is also included, with classifications for heating, cooling, lighting, EV, and electrical appliances. This taxonomy can be useful in understanding and analysing energy consumption patterns and developing strategies for optimizing energy usage.
Scope	The Energy-Consumption-Pattern taxonomy classifies various aspects of energy consumption, including location, unit of measurement, sector, usage patterns, energy sources, and usage types, for understanding and optimizing energy usage.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: dateTime, string, int

Table 17: Energy Consumption Pattern Conceptual Taxonomy

Energy Consumption Pattern

Property

- Location
- Unit of measurement
 - Electricity Consumption: kilowatt-hour (kWh)
 - Liquid Fuel Consumption: Tons oil equivalent (toe)
 - Solid Fuel Consumption: Cubic meters (m³)
- Value
- Date-Time

Energy Consumption

- Sector
 - Residential
 - Commercial
 - Industrial

Energy Usage Pattern

- Hourly
- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly

Energy Source

Renewable Energy Source

- Solar Energy Source
- Wind Energy Source
- Hydro Energy Source
- Bio Energy Source

Non Renewable Energy Source

- Fossil Fuel Energy Source
 - Coal Energy Source
 - Oil Energy Source
 - Natural Gas Energy Source

Usage Type

- Heating

- Cooling
- Lighting
- EV
- Electrical Appliances

Energy Consumption and usage patterns Conceptual Properties:

- hasData&Time
- hasLocation
- hasMeasurement
- hasSector
- hasUsagePattern
- hasValeu
- usesEnergySource
 - hasNonRES
 - hasRES
- usesEnergySourceType

8.3.1.8. Energy storage systems and technologies Conceptualization

Table 18: Conceptualization of Energy Storage Systems and Technologies ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Energy_Storage_Systems_and_Technologies
Description	Energy storage systems and technologies refer to the various methods and devices used for storing energy to be used at a later time. The taxonomy for this field can be organized into several categories, including energy storage technologies, system configurations, applications, and materials. Energy storage technologies include electrochemical, mechanical, thermal, and electrical energy storage. System configurations refer to how the energy storage system is arranged, such as grid-connected, off-grid, or hybrid systems. Applications of energy storage include peak shaving, frequency regulation, and backup power. Materials used in energy storage systems can be organic, inorganic, or hybrid. In addition, energy storage systems can be classified based on their scale, ranging from small-scale residential systems to large-scale grid-level systems. Effective deployment of energy storage systems and technologies can increase the reliability, efficiency, and flexibility of energy systems and can help to integrate renewable energy sources into the grid.
Scope	The Energy storage systems and technologies taxonomy classifies various aspects of energy storage, including technologies, system configurations, applications, materials, and scale, for enhancing energy system reliability, efficiency, and renewable energy integration.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX

Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string
-------------------------------	-------------

Table 19: Energy Storage Systems Technologies Conceptual Taxonomy
Energy Storage Systems Technologies

- BESS system
 - Lithium ion batteries
 - Lead acid batteries
 - Sodium ion batteries
 - Flow batteries
 - Redox batteries
 - Supercapacitors
- Mechanical Energy Storage Systems
 - Pumped hydroelectric storage
 - Compressed air energy storage
 - Flywheels
- Thermal Energy Storage Systems
 - Sensible heat storage
 - Latent heat storage
 - Thermochemical storage
 - Phase change materials
- Electrostatic Energy Storage Systems
 - Capacitors
- Other Energy Storage Systems
 - Hydrogen storage
 - Methane storage
 - Ammonia storage
 - Thermal energy in buildings (e.g., hot water tanks)
- Hybrid Storage System
 - Combine two or more systems

Energy Storage Systems Technologies Conceptual Properties:

- hasBESSsystem
- hasElectrostaticStorage
- hasHybrid
- hasOtherStorage
- StoresMechanically
- StoresThermally

8.3.1.9. Smart Devices Conceptualization

Table 20: Conceptualization of Smart Devices ontology

Ontologies Metadata Used	
Title	DATACELLAR/Smart_Devices
Description	The classification taxonomy for the class "Device" provides a detailed framework for understanding two significant types of devices used in the energy sector - EnergyRelated and WeatherRelated . Smart meters, which fall under the EnergyRelated category, are instrumental in energy management, enabling the measurement and calculation of energy consumption data, and facilitating billing

	procedures. They measure current and voltage, associate them to calculate active and reactive power, and calculate energy consumed over a given time interval. In contrast, WeatherRelated devices, represented by sensors, measure weather-related variables, including ambient temperature, solar irradiation, wind speed, and ambient noise, and are essential for real-time weather monitoring to optimize energy generation and distribution. By providing a comprehensive overview of the functions, properties, and measurements associated with these devices, this taxonomy serves as a useful tool for researchers, developers, and stakeholders in the energy sector.
Scope	The Energy storage systems and technologies taxonomy classifies various aspects of energy storage, including technologies, system configurations, applications, materials, and scale, for enhancing energy system reliability, efficiency, and renewable energy integration.
Authors/Contributors	DATA CELLAR WP3 consortium
Ontological Annotations	Included in the respective RDF file of the ANNEX
Types of data in the ontology	xsd: string, float, byte, dateTime, int

Table 21: Smart Devices Conceptual Taxonomy
Smart Devices

Energy-Related (smart meter)

- Function ER

- Measure current and voltage
- Associate them to calculate active and reactive power
- Calculate energy consumed in a time interval

Property ER

- Measure data
- Store data
- Send data for billing procedure

Measurement ER

Unit of measurement ER

- Current: Ampere (A)
- Voltage: Volt (V)
- Power
 - Active: kilowatt (kW)
 - Reactive: kilovolt-ampere reactive (kVA_r)
 - Apparent: kilovolt-ampere (kVA)
- Power factor: w/o dimension
- Energy: kilowatt-hour (kWh)

Weather-Related (sensor)

Function WR

- Measure weather-related variables
- Wind Power
- Hydro Power
- Geothermal Power

Property WR

- Measure data
- Stores data
- Send data to a database

Measurement WR

Unit of measurement WR

- Ambient temperature: degrees Celsius (°C)
- Solar irradiation: Watt per square meter (Wm2)
- Wind speed: meter per second (ms-1)
- Ambient noise: decibels (dB)

Smart Devices Conceptual Properties:

- hasERFunction
- hasPropertyER
- hasPropertyWR
- hasWRFunction
- MeasuresER
- MeasuresWR

9. DATA CELLAR Ontology in Protégé Framework

PROTÉGÉ, a renowned ontology editor and framework, is a powerful open-source tool developed by the esteemed Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research⁶³. With its adaptable plug-and-play environment, it enables users to create knowledge-driven solutions, providing a versatile foundation for rapid prototyping. In D3.1, we leverage the robust desktop application of PROTÉGÉ, which empowers the DATA CELLAR ontology developers to generate RDF files, seamlessly migrate data using multiple methods, and achieve visual optimizations of the ontologies. The subsequent sections, present the visually captivating representations of the ontologies crafted by harnessing the potential of the conceptual version. In addition, the RDF scripts generated by PROTÉGÉ are hosted in the ANNEX:

9.1. Ontology Representation

9.1.1. Knowledge Graphs / OWLViz

OWLviz is designed for visualizing complex ontological trees represented in OWL. By leveraging OWLviz, one generates comprehensive and interactive graphical representations that accurately depict the intricate network of classes, properties, and relationships within an ontology. This visualization not only enhances the comprehension of the ontology structure but also facilitates seamless navigation through its interconnected components. Via OWLviz, the ontology developers and domain experts can effortlessly explore and analyze through ontology's architecture, unraveling the intricate relationships and dependencies between different concepts. The graphical representation employs intuitive visual elements such as nodes to represent classes and properties, and edges to signify the relationships and associations between them. The layout of the diagram is automatically generated, intelligently arranging the elements to optimize clarity and readability. The utilization of OWLviz significantly simplifies the comprehension and interpretation of complex ontologies. It aids in identifying hierarchical structures, uncovering semantic connections, and discerning patterns and clusters within the ontology. The list of OWLViz representations of the DATA CELLAR ontologies demonstrated below:

⁶³ <https://bmir.stanford.edu/>

Figure 11: OWLViz Graph of Energy Market Structures and Pricing Ontology

Figure 12: OWLviz Graph of Energy Regulations Policies and Standards Ontology

Figure 13: OWL Viz Graph of Energy efficiency technologies Ontology

Figure 14: OWLViz Graph of Energy generation technologies and sources Ontology

Figure 15: OWLViz Graph of Energy Generation Ontology

Figure 16: OWLViz Graph of Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems

Figure 17: OWLViz Graph of Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns

Figure 18: OWLViz Graph of Energy Storage Systems Technologies

Figure 19: OWLViz Graph of Smart Devices

9.1.2. OntoGraf / RDF Graphs

The core structure of the abstract syntax is a set of triples, each consisting of a subject, a predicate, and an objective. These are translated via the classification family levels (subjects and objects) and the properties (predicates). An RDF graph can be visualized as a node and directed-arc diagram, in which each triple is represented as a node-arc-node link, however, the DATA CELLAR RDF graphs demonstrated in this section do not bear the node-description to facilitate the visual representation. This is represented with the nodes demonstrated in various colours. PROTEGE OntoGrafs are the ontology RDF graphs or schemas that combine the strengths of ontology modelling and graph-based representations.

Figure 20: RDF Graph of Energy Market Structures and Pricing Ontology

Figure 21: RDF Graph of Energy Regulations Policies and Standards

Figure 22: RDF Graph of Energy efficiency technologies

Figure 23: RDF Graph of Energy Conservation Practices

Figure 24: RDF Graph of Energy Generation Technologies and Sources

Figure 25: RDF Graph of Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems

Figure 26: RDF Graph of Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns

Figure 27: RDF Graph of Energy Storage Systems Technologies

Figure 28: RDF Graph of Smart Devices

9.1.3. Knowledge Graphs / OWL

Although the phrase “knowledge graph” appeared as early as 1972, the modern incarnation of the term stems from the 2012 announcement of the Google Knowledge Graph, followed by further announcements of knowledge graphs by other companies including Amazon, Facebook, and Microsoft. Ehrlinger and Wöß⁶⁴ have developed a definition from knowledge graph architecture and a terminological analysis, which indicates that “A knowledge graph acquires and integrates information into an ontology and applies a reasoner to derive new knowledge”. A knowledge graph, often referred to as a semantic network, embodies a complex interconnection of real-world entities encompassing objects, events, situations, or concepts, while elucidating the intricate web of relationships that bind them. Typically residing within a graph database, this wealth of information manifests as a graph structure, thereby justifying its designation as a knowledge graph. In PROTÉGÉ, the Visual Notation for OWL Ontologies (VOWL) is a well-specified visual language for the user-oriented representation of ontologies. It defines graphical depictions for most elements of the OWL that are combined to a force-directed graph layout visualizing the ontology⁶⁵. VOWL aims for an intuitive and comprehensive representation that is also understandable to users less familiar with ontologies. D3.1 leverages primarily the ProtégéVOWL add-on for the development of the following knowledge graphs. However, only the graph associated with the Smart Devices ontology (Figure 37) was developed in the web-based version of VOWL.

64 Ehrlinger, Lisa & Wöß, Wolfram. (2016). *Towards a Definition of Knowledge Graphs*.

65 Alani. *TGVizTab: An ontology visualisation extension for Protégé*. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Visualizing Information in Knowledge Engineering (VIKE '03)*, 200

Figure 29: Knowledge Graph of Energy Market Structures and Pricing Ontology

Figure 30: Knowledge Graph of Energy Regulations Policies and Standards

Figure 31: Knowledge Graph of Energy efficiency technologies

Figure 32: Knowledge Graph of Energy Conservation Practices

Figure 33: Knowledge Graph of Energy Generation Technologies and Sources

Figure 34: Knowledge Graph of Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems

Figure 35: Knowledge Graph of Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns

Figure 36: Knowledge Graph of Energy Storage Systems Technologies

Figure 37: Knowledge Graph of Smart Devices

10. Conclusions and Future Directions

In this report, the “Ontology with well-defined taxonomy and metadata for the targeted databases agreed and reported” is detailed with exhaustive reference to the status in Ontology practices with specific emphasis to the disciplines of energy.

Emphasis has been given to the existing or currently running practices in the field, by providing an in-depth exploration of the prevailing EU databases within the specific context of data and information that exhibit significant pertinence to the validation cases of DATA CELLAR. Knowing that the current objective of DATA CELLAR is to construct an ontology specifically tailored to the energy domain serving the energy communities, the current report provides a comprehensive account of the procedural stages involved in implementing the LOT methodology for the development of the energy domain ontology.

For this purpose, the aim through the work within T3.1 reported in this deliverable, is to leverage relevant databases, such as energy, environment-related repositories, and respective linked data. One of the key benefits of using relevant databases is presented as the access to energy and environment-related repositories. These repositories are dedicated to collecting and organizing data pertaining to energy and/or environmental data. They can act as valuable resources for the DATA CELLAR ontology developers, since they provide a wealth of information about the entities, attributes, and relationships that exist within these domains. This, linked data, plays a significant role in supporting ontology development.

In the paragraphs above, specific emphasis is given to understand the role and purpose of ontologies and how these can form the basis of traceability and interoperability. In Section 0 above, the proposed methodology concerning ontology development to be applied for the DATA CELLAR energy domain is presented in detail. As concluded through a detailed presentation of current practices in Section 0, the DATA CELLAR methodology is based primarily on the **Linked Open Terms (LOT)**⁶⁶ methodology, and partially on the **METHONTOLOGY**⁶⁷.

In Section 4 the following attributes of the process are detailed since they play a crucial role in the development of a dependable ontology of the planned DATA CELLAR data space:

- Taxonomies
- Metadata
- Data and metadata Schemas
- Knowledge Graphs

In Section 5 the DATA CELLAR Ontology Development Methodology is presented giving the evidence for the choices made in adapting the LOT principles, while METHONTOLOGY elements are exploited to enhance the development process where relevant.

⁶⁶ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

⁶⁷ Gomez-Perez, Asuncion & Fernández-López, Mariano & Corcho, Oscar. (2004). *Ontological Engineering: With Examples from the Areas of Knowledge Management, E-Commerce and the Semantic Web*.

Section 6 analyses the importance of ontologies Reuse in DATA CELLAR. Stressing that developing Local Energy Communities (LEC) is a multidisciplinary research activity since engineering, economics, and meteorology experts often work together. For this reason, a common vocabulary that described the players (human beings and devices) and their possible interactions is mandatory to properly interact. Moreover, if well-designed, already existing ontologies can be reused, increasing the integration and interoperability of different systems. For this reason, care is taken in this section to briefly describe the existing ontologies that have been reused to implement the DATA CELLAR energy domain ontology, under the LOT - implementation step. Five such existing ontologies have been presented with details to validate the importance of using them.

Section 7 the methodology for data Migration between Ontologies is presented to ascertain the pursued interoperability principles that can be adapted from and to the DATA CELLAR ontology. Hence the procedure for converting data in different formats into an RDF graph that adheres to the DATA CELLAR ontology is analysed.

Section 8 addresses the issues related to DATA CELLAR Ontology Conceptualization as an input to the PROTÉGÉ encoding that is used as the adapted method within DATA CELLAR. The importance in implementing this step is the fact that domain-specific ontologies serve as means to define the ontological agreements and commitments between information providers and users within an information infrastructure.

Exploring this need, the report tabulates the attributes of the selected ontological categories addressed by the DATA CELLAR which are:

- Energy market structures and pricing;
- Energy regulations, policies, and standards;
- Energy efficiency technologies;
- Energy generation technologies and sources;
- Energy transmission and distribution systems;
- Energy consumption and usage patterns;
- Energy storage systems and technologies;
- Smart Devices.

In Section 9 details are presented of the capabilities of the PROTÉGÉ framework selected for the DATA CELLAR Ontology. As can be appreciated, the solutions presented in this report are not publicly available and further steps are expected as work progresses in the next phases of the project, and these are indicated below:

- The ontology is to be made publicly available in publicly accessible platforms (such as zenodo) in the future during the course of the project.
- Some of the evaluation steps are not fully addressed since the ontology is only available in the boundaries of SharePoint.
- The relevant hosting URIs cannot be published due to the premature status of the ontology as currently developed.

- **The evaluation stage under D3.1 involves an initial assessment since the ontology is not published online before the deliverable's finalization. The online publication requires the completion of data model and a more finalized status of interoperability.**

11. ANNEX

Figure 38: OWLDoc of the Energy Market and Pricing Ontology

11.1. Indicative HTML scripts

```
HTML script for Energy Market and Pricing Ontology
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Market Structure Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Market Structure</h1>
<ul>
<li>Wholesale Energy Markets
<ul>
<li>Market Types
<ul>
<li>Spot Markets</li>
<li>Forward Markets</li>
<li>Futures Markets</li>
<li>Options Markets</li>
<li>Day-Ahead Markets</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Market Mechanisms
<ul>
<li>Auctions</li>
<li>Bilateral Contracts</li>
<li>Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)</li>
<li>Net Metering</li>
<li>Feed-in Tariffs (FITs)</li>
<li>Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Market Participants
<ul>
<li>Suppliers</li>
<li>Consumers</li>
<li>Brokers</li>
<li>Aggregators</li>
<li>Independent System Operators (ISOs)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Regulatory Structures
<ul>
<li>Deregulated Markets</li>
<li>Regulated Markets</li>
<li>Market Power Mitigation</li>
<li>Anti-Trust Laws</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>
```

```

</ul>
</li>
<li>Retail-Energy Markets
  <ul>
    <li>Residential</li>
    <li>Commercial</li>
    <li>Industrial</li>
    <li>Government and Institutional</li>
  </ul>
</li>
<li>Pricing Model
  <ul>
    <li>Cost-based Pricing</li>
    <li>Marginal Cost Pricing</li>
    <li>Average Cost Pricing</li>
    <li>Time-of-Use Pricing</li>
    <li>Real-Time Pricing</li>
    <li>Inclining Block Rates</li>
  </ul>
</li>
</ul>
<h2>Energy Market and Pricing Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
  <li>hasMarketMechanism</li>
  <li>hasMarketParticipants</li>
  <li>hasMarketType</li>
  <li>hasPricingModel</li>
  <li>hasRegulatoryStructures</li>
  <li>hasRetailEnergyMarkets</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

26. HTML script for Energy Regulations, Policies, and standards Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
  <title>Energy Regulations Policies Standards Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Energy Regulations Policies Standards</h1>
  <ul>
    <li>Policy and Regulatory Bodies
      <ul>
        <li>National Energy Regulators
          <ul>
            <li>Member States Authorities</li>
          </ul>
        </li>
        <li>International Energy Agencies
          <ul>
            <li>IEA</li>
            <li>IRENA</li>
            <li>OACED</li>
            <li>REN21</li>
          </ul>
        </li>
        <li>Government Energy Ministries
          <ul>
            <li>Member States Ministries</li>
          </ul>
        </li>
        <li>Environmental Protection Agencies</li>
        <li>Public Utilities Commissions</li>
        <li>Other Relevant Government Departments</li>
      </ul>
    </li>
    <li>Energy Policy Types
      <ul>
        <li>Renewable Energy</li>
        <li>Energy Efficiency</li>
        <li>Climate Change Mitigation</li>
        <li>Energy Security</li>
        <li>Sustainable Development</li>
      </ul>
    </li>
    <li>Energy Policy Instruments
      <ul>
        <li>Feed-In Tariffs (FITs)</li>
        <li>Net-Metering</li>
        <li>Tax Incentives</li>
        <li>Carbon Pricing</li>
        <li>Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS)</li>
        <li>Energy Efficiency Standards</li>
        <li>Energy Performance Certificates</li>
        <li>Building Codes & Standards</li>
        <li>Appliance & Equipment Efficiency Standards</li>
      </ul>
    </li>
    <li>International Energy Agreements & Standards
      <ul>
        <li>Paris Agreement</li>
        <li>Kyoto Protocol</li>
        <li>IECC</li>
        <li>ISO energy management standards</li>
        <li>IEC energy standards</li>
      </ul>
    </li>
    <li>Energy Market Regulations

```



```

        <li>Vinyl</li>
        <li>Fiberglass</li>
    </ul>
</li>
<li>Window Glazing
    <ul>
        <li>Single Pane</li>
        <li>Double Pane</li>
        <li>Triple Pane</li>
        <li>Low E-Coating</li>
        <li>Gas Filled Windows</li>
        <li>Tinted Windows</li>
    </ul>
</li>
<li>Door Types
    <ul>
        <li>Hinged</li>
        <li>Sliding</li>
        <li>Bi-Fold</li>
    </ul>
</li>
<li>Door Materials
    <ul>
        <li>Wood</li>
        <li>Steel</li>
        <li>Fiberglass</li>
        <li>Aluminum</li>
    </ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Vapor Barriers</li>
<li>Insulation
    <ul>
        <li>Material based
            <ul>
                <li>Fiberglass</li>
                <li>Mineral wool</li>
                <li>Cellulose</li>
                <li>Reflective</li>
                <li>Radiant barrier</li>
                <li>Aerogel</li>
                <li>Polystyrene</li>
                <li>Natural insulation (wool, cotton, straw, etc.)</li>
            </ul>
        </li>
        <li>Use case based
            <ul>
                <li>Attic insulation</li>
                <li>Wall insulation</li>
                <li>Floor insulation</li>
                <li>Pipe insulation</li>
                <li>Duct insulation</li>
            </ul>
        </li>
        <li>Performance based
            <ul>
                <li>High performance</li>
                <li>Low VOC</li>
                <li>Fire resistant</li>
                <li>Soundproofing</li>
                <li>Moisture resistant</li>
            </ul>
        </li>
    </ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Energy Efficient Appliances & Equipment
    <ul>
        <li>Refrigerators & Freezers</li>
        <li>Dishwashers</li>
        <li>Clothes Washers</li>
        <li>Clothes Dryers</li>
        <li>Air Conditioners</li>
        <li>Furnaces & Boilers</li>
        <li>Heat Pumps</li>
        <li>Water Heaters</li>
    </ul>
</li>
<li>Industrial Process & Manufacturing Technologies
    <ul>
        <li>Material Handling & Storage</li>
        <li>HVAC</li>
        <li>Automation & Control</li>
    </ul>
</li>
</ul>
<h2>Energy Efficient Technologies Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
    <li>hasApplianceEquipment</li>
    <li>hasBuildingEnvelope
        <ul>
            <li>hasInsulation
                <ul>
                    <li>basedOn</li>
                </ul>
            </li>
        </ul>
    </li>
</ul>

```

```

<li>hasOpenings</li>
<li>hasRoof</li>
<li>hasVaporBarrier</li>
<li>hasWalls</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>hasHVAC</li>
<li>hasLightingSystem</li>
<li>IndustrialProcess</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

28. HTML script for Energy Conservation Practices Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Energy Conservation Practices Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Energy Conservation Practices</h1>
<ul>
<li>Behavioural practices
<ul>
<li>Energy efficient habits</li>
<li>Efficient use of energy consuming devices</li>
<li>Energy audits & assessments</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Building systems optimization
<ul>
<li>HVAC optimization</li>
<li>Lighting optimization</li>
<li>Building envelope optimization</li>
<li>Water conservation measures</li>
<li>Renewable energy systems installation</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Transportation
<ul>
<li>Fuel efficient vehicles</li>
<li>EVs</li>
<li>Public transportation</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
<h2>Energy Conservation Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
<li>hasConsercationPractice</li>
<li>hasPractices</li>
<li>systemOptimization</li>
<li>Transportation</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

29. HTML script for Energy Generation Technologies and Sources Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Energy Generation Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Energy Generation</h1>
<ul>
<li>Primary Energy Generation
<ul>
<li>Fossil Fuels
<ul>
<li>Coal</li>
<li>Oil</li>
<li>Natural Gas</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Biomass</li>
<li>Renewable Energy Sources
<ul>
<li>Solar Power</li>
<li>Wind Power</li>
<li>Hydro Power</li>
<li>Geothermal Power</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Secondary Energy Generation
<ul>
<li>Electricity Generation</li>
<li>Heat Generation</li>
<li>CHP (Combined Heat and Power systems)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Measurement
<ul>
<li>Unit of measurement

```

```

        <ul>
          <li>Electricity Generation: kilowatt hour (kWh)</li>
          <li>Liquid Fuel: Tons oil equivalent (toe)</li>
          <li>Solid Fuel: Cubic meters (m3)</li>
        </ul>
      </li>
    </ul>
  </li>
</ul>
<h2>Energy Generation Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
  <li>hasEnergySource</li>
  <li>hasMeasurement</li>
  <li>hasSecondaryGeneration</li>
  <li>hasUnitOfMeasurement</li>
  <li>hasFuelType</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

30. HTML script for Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
  <title>Energy Transmission and Distribution System Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Energy Transmission and Distribution System</h1>
  <ul>
    <li>Property
      <ul>
        <li>Location
          <ul>
            <li>Rural</li>
            <li>Urban</li>
          </ul>
        </li>
        <li>Operator</li>
        <li>Capacity</li>
        <li>Length</li>
        <li>StartDate</li>
        <li>Technologies</li>
        <li>Purpose</li>
        <li>Energy Commodity
          <ul>
            <li>Electricity
              <ul>
                <li>Renewable Electricity
                  <ul>
                    <li>Solar Electricity</li>
                    <li>Wind Electricity</li>
                    <li>Hydro Electricity</li>
                    <li>Bio Electricity</li>
                  </ul>
                </li>
                <li>Non-Renewable Electricity
                  <ul>
                    <li>Fossil Fuel Electricity
                      <ul>
                        <li>Coal Electricity</li>
                        <li>Oil Electricity</li>
                        <li>Natural Gas Electricity</li>
                      </ul>
                    </li>
                    <li>Natural Gas</li>
                    <li>Oil</li>
                  </ul>
                </li>
                <li>Electrical Grid
                  <ul>
                    <li>Current Type
                      <ul>
                        <li>Alternative Current (AC)</li>
                        <li>Direct Current (DC)</li>
                      </ul>
                    </li>
                    <li>Voltage Level
                      <ul>
                        <li>Low Voltage (LV)</li>
                        <li>Medium Voltage (MV)</li>
                        <li>High Voltage (HV)</li>
                      </ul>
                    </li>
                  </ul>
                </li>
                <li>Pipeline System
                  <ul>
                    <li>Pressure
                      <ul>
                        <li>Low</li>
                        <li>High</li>
                      </ul>
                    </li>
                  </ul>
                </li>
              </ul>
            </li>
          </ul>
        </li>
      </ul>
    </li>
  </ul>

```

```

</ul>
</li>
</ul>
<h2>Properties</h2>
<ul>
<li>hasCapacity</li>
<li>hasCurrentType</li>
<li>hasElectricitySource</li>
<li>hasElectricityType</li>
<li>hasEnergyCommodity</li>
<li>hasLength</li>
<li>hasLocation</li>
<li>hasOperator</li>
<li>hasPipelineSystem</li>
<li>hasTechnologies</li>
<li>hasVoltageType</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

31. HTML script for Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Energy Consumption Pattern</h1>
<ul>
<li>Property
<ul>
<li>Location</li>
<li>Unit of measurement
<ul>
<li>Electricity Consumption: kilowatt-hour (kWh)</li>
<li>Liquid Fuel Consumption: Tons oil equivalent (toe)</li>
<li>Solid Fuel Consumption: Cubic meters (m3)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Value</li>
<li>Date-Time</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Energy Consumption
<ul>
<li>Sector
<ul>
<li>Residential</li>
<li>Commercial</li>
<li>Industrial</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Energy Usage Pattern
<ul>
<li>Hourly</li>
<li>Daily</li>
<li>Weekly</li>
<li>Monthly</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Energy Source
<ul>
<li>Renewable Energy Source
<ul>
<li>Solar Energy Source</li>
<li>Wind Energy Source</li>
<li>Hydro Energy Source</li>
<li>Bio Energy Source</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Non-Renewable Energy Source
<ul>
<li>Fossil Fuel Energy Source
<ul>
<li>Coal Energy Source</li>
<li>Oil Energy Source</li>
<li>Natural Gas Energy Source</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Usage Type
<ul>
<li>Heating</li>
<li>Cooling</li>
<li>Lighting</li>
<li>EV</li>
<li>Electrical Appliances</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</body>
<h2>Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
<li>hasData&Time</li>
<li>hasLocation</li>

```

```

</li>hasMeasurement</li>
</li>hasSector</li>
</li>hasUsagePattern</li>
</li>hasValue</li>
</li>usesEnergySource</li>
</ul>
</li>hasNonRES</li>
</li>hasRES</li>
</ul>
</li>usesEnergySourceType</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

32. HTML script for Energy Storage Systems and Technologies Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Energy Storage Systems Technologies Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Energy Storage Systems Technologies</h1>
<ul>
<li>BESS system
<ul>
<li>Lithium ion batteries</li>
<li>Lead acid batteries</li>
<li>Sodium ion batteries</li>
<li>Flow batteries</li>
<li>Redox batteries</li>
<li>Supercapacitors</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Mechanical Energy Storage Systems
<ul>
<li>Pumped hydroelectric storage</li>
<li>Compressed air energy storage</li>
<li>Flywheels</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Thermal Energy Storage Systems
<ul>
<li>Sensible heat storage</li>
<li>Latent heat storage</li>
<li>Thermochemical storage</li>
<li>Phase change materials</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Electrostatic Energy Storage Systems
<ul>
<li>Capacitors</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Other Energy Storage Systems
<ul>
<li>Hydrogen storage</li>
<li>Methane storage</li>
<li>Ammonia storage</li>
<li>Thermal energy in buildings (e.g., hot water tanks)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Hybrid Storage System
<ul>
<li>Combine two or more systems</li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
<h2>Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
<li>hasBESSsystem</li>
<li>hasElectrostaticStorage</li>
<li>hasHybrid</li>
<li>hasOtherStorage</li>
<li>StoresMechanically</li>
<li>StoresThermally</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

33. HTML script for Smart Devices Ontology

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Smart Devices Ontology</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Smart Devices</h1>
<h2>Energy-Related (smart meter)</h2>
<h3>Function ER</h3>
<ul>
<li>Measure current and voltage</li>
<li>Associate them to calculate active and reactive power</li>
<li>Calculate energy consumed in a time interval</li>
</ul>
<h3>Property ER</h3>
<ul>

```

```

<li>Measure data</li>
<li>Store data</li>
<li>Send data for billing procedure</li>
</ul>
<h3>Measurement ER</h3>
<h4>Unit of measurement ER</h4>
<ul>
<li>Current: Ampere (A)</li>
<li>Voltage: Volt (V)</li>
<li>Power
  <ul>
<li>Active: kilowatt (kW)</li>
<li>Reactive: kilovolt-ampere reactive (kVA_r)</li>
<li>Apparent: kilovolt-ampere (kVA)</li>
</ul>
</li>
<li>Power factor: w/o dimension</li>
<li>Energy: kilowatt-hour (kWh)</li>
</ul>
<h2>Weather-Related (sensor)</h2>
<h3>Function WR</h3>
<ul>
<li>Measure weather-related variables</li>
<li>Wind Power</li>
<li>Hydro Power</li>
<li>Geothermal Power</li>
</ul>
<h3>Property WR</h3>
<ul>
<li>Measure data</li>
<li>Store data</li>
<li>Send data to a database</li>
</ul>
<h3>Measurement WR</h3>
<h4>Unit of measurement WR</h4>
<ul>
<li>Ambient temperature: degrees Celsius (oC)</li>
<li>Solar irradiation: Watt per square meter (Wm2)</li>
<li>Wind speed: meter per second (ms-1)</li>
<li>Ambient noise: decibels (dB)</li>
</ul>
<h2>Conceptual Properties</h2>
<ul>
<li>hasERFunction</li>
<li>hasPropertyER</li>
<li>hasPropertyWR</li>
<li>hasWRFunction</li>
<li>MeasuresER</li>
<li>MeasuresWR</li>
</ul>
</body>
</html>

```

11.2. Indicative RDF scripts

1. RDF script for Energy Market and Pricing Ontology

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/EnergyMarket">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/EnergyMarket"/>
<!--
//
// Data properties
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketMechnism
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketMechnism"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketParticipants
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketParticipants"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketTypes
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketTypes"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#PricingModel
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#PricingModel">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketMechnism"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketParticipants"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#MarketTypes"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Regulatory"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#RetailMarket"/>
<rdf:type rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#FunctionalProperty"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Regulatory
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Regulatory"/>
<!--

```

```

http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#RetailMarket
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#RetailMarket"/>
<!-- http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty -->
<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty">
<rdf:type rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#FunctionalProperty"/>
</rdf:Description>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Aggregators
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Aggregators">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Participants"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Anti-Trust_Laws
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Anti-Trust_Laws">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Regulatory_Structures"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Auctions
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Auctions">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Mechanisms"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Average_Cost_Pricing
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Average_Cost_Pricing">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Pricing_model"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Bilateral_Contracts
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Bilateral_Contracts">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Mechanisms"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Brokers
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Brokers">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Participants"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Commercial
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Commercial">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Retail_energy_markets"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Consumers
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Consumers">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Participants"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Cost-based_Pricing
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Cost-based_Pricing">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Pricing_model"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Day-Ahead_Markets
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Day-Ahead_Markets">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Deregulated_Markets
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Deregulated_Markets">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Regulatory_Structures"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Forward_Markets
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Forward_Markets">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Futures_Markets
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Futures_Markets">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Government_and_Institutional
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Government_and_Institutional">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Retail_energy_markets"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Inclining_Block_Rates

```



```
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Wholesale_energy_markets
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Wholesale_energy_markets">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Feed-in_Tariffs_(FITs)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Feed-in_Tariffs_(FITs)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Mechanisms"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Independent_System_Operators_(ISOs)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Independent_System_Operators_(ISOs)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Participants"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Power_Purchase_Agreements_(PPAs)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Power_Purchase_Agreements_(PPAs)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Mechanisms"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Renewable_Portfolio_Standards_(RPS)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Renewable_Portfolio_Standards_(RPS)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/energy_market_pricing#Market_Mechanisms"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>
```

2. RDF script for Energy Regulations Policies and Standards Ontology

```
<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/Energy_Regulations_Policies_Standards">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/Energy_Regulations_Policies_Standards">
<!--
//
// Classes
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Carbon_Pricing
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Carbon_Pricing">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Climate_Change_Mitigation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Climate_Change_Mitigation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Efficiency
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Efficiency">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Efficiency_Standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Efficiency_Standards">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Market_Regulations
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Market_Regulations">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Performance_Certificates
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Performance_Certificates">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Security
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Security">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Environmental
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Environmental">
```

```

<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Environmental_Protection_Agencies
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Environmental_Protection_Agencies">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Government_Energy_Ministries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Government_Energy_Ministries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IEA
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IEA">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IECC
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IECC">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IEC_energy_standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IEC_energy_standards">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IRENA
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#IRENA">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#ISO_energy_management_standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#ISO_energy_management_standards">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Kyoto_Protocol
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Kyoto_Protocol">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Market_Design
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Market_Design">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Member_States_Authorities
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Member_States_Authorities">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#National_Energy_Regulators"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Member_States_Ministries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Member_States_Ministries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Government_Energy_Ministries"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#National_Energy_Regulators
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#National_Energy_Regulators">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Net-Metering
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Net-Metering">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#OACED
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#OACED">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Other_Relevant_Government_Departments
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Other_Relevant_Government_Departments">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Paris_Agreement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Paris_Agreement">

```

```

<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Public_Utilities_Commissions
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Public_Utilities_Commissions">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Policy_and_Regulatory_Bodies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#REN21
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#REN21">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agencies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Energy
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Energy">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Energy_Integration
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Energy_Integration">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Retail_Competition
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Retail_Competition">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Safety
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Safety">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Sustainable_Development
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Sustainable_Development">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Tax_Incentives
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Tax_Incentives">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Appliance&Equipment_Efficiency_Standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Appliance&Equipment_Efficiency_Standards">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Building_Codes&Standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Building_Codes&Standards">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Exploration&Production
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Exploration&Production">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Feed-In_Tariffs_(FITs)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Feed-In_Tariffs_(FITs)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#International_Energy_Agreements&Standards"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Market_Monitoring&Enforcement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Market_Monitoring&Enforcement">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Refining&Distribution
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Refining&Distribution">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Portfolio_Standards_(RPS)

```

```
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Renewable_Portfolio_Standards_(RPS)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Energy_Policy_Instruments"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Transmission&Distribution_System
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Transmission&Distribution_System">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Electricity_Market_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Transportation&Storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Transportation&Storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-27#Oil&Gas_Industry_Regulations"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>
```

3. RDF script for Energy Efficient Technologies Ontology

```

rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Efficiency_TEchnologies">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Efficiency_TEchnologies"/>
<!--
//
// Object Properties
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#basedOn
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#basedOn">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasInsulation"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasDoorMaterials
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasDoorMaterials">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasDoorTypes
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasDoorTypes">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasInsulation
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasInsulation">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasNumberOfOpenings
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasNumberOfOpenings">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasRoof
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasRoof">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasVaporBarrier
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasVaporBarrier">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWalls
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWalls">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasBuildingEnvelope"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowFrame
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowFrame">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowGlazing
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowGlazing">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>

```

```

</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowTypes
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasWindowTypes">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#hasOpenings"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Data properties
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Openings
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Openings">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Roof
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Roof">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_Envelope_Systems"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aerogel
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aerogel">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Air_Conditioners
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Air_Conditioners">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aluminum
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aluminum">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Frames"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aluminum_door
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Aluminum_door">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Door_Materials"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Attic_insulation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Attic_insulation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Use_case_based"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Awning
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Awning">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_envelope_systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_envelope_systems">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Casement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Casement">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Types"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Cellulose
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Cellulose">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based"/>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Central
-->
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#HVAC_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Clothes_Dryers
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Clothes_Washers
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Concrete
-->
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Dishwashers
-->
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<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Door_Materials
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Door_Types
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Double_Hung
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Double_Pane
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Double_Pane">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Duct_insulation
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Fiberglass
-->
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based"/>
</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Fire_resistant
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Flat_roofing
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Flat_roofing">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Floor_insulation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Floor_insulation">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Fluorescent
-->
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Gas_Filled_Windows
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Gas_Filled_Windows">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing"/>
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<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Geothermal
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Green_roofing
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Heat_Pump
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Heat_Pump">
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Heat_Pumps
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Heat_Pumps">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#High_performance
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Hinged
-->
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Incandescent
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Incandescent">
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#LED
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Lighting_systems
-->
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Low_E-Coating
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Low_VOC
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Low_VOC">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Masonry
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation"/>
</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Mineral_wool
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<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Moisture_resistant
-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Number_of_openening
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</owl:Class>
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-->
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Overall_Insulation_Performance
-->
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#PVC
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#PVC">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Packaged
-->
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</owl:Class>
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-->
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Pipe_insulation
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Use_case_based"/>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Pitched_roofing
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Roof"/>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Polystyrene
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Radiant_barrier
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Reflective
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</owl:Class>
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Single_Hung
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Single_Pane
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<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing"/>
</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Sliding
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Sliding_Doors
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Smart
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Smart">
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Solar_roofing
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Soundproofing
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</owl:Class>
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http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Steel
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</owl:Class>
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<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Steel_door">
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</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Tinted_Windows
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Tinted_Windows">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Triple_Pane
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Triple_Pane">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Use_case_based
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Use_case_based">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Insulation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Vapor_Barriers
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Vapor_Barriers">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_envelope_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Vinyl
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Vinyl">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Frames"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wall_insulation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wall_insulation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Use_case_based"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Building_envelope_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Water_Heaters
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Water_Heaters">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_AC
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_AC">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#HVAC_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Frames
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Frames">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Openings"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Glazing">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Openings"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--

```

```

http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Types
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Types">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Openings"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wood
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wood">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wooden_Frame
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wooden_Frame">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Window_Frames"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wooden_door
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Wooden_door">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Door_Materials"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Automation&Control
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Automation&Control">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Industrial_Process&Manufacturing_Technologies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Furnaces&Boilers
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Furnaces&Boilers">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#ICF_(Insulated_concrete_forms)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#ICF_(Insulated_concrete_forms)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Walls"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Industrial_Process&Manufacturing_Technologies
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Industrial_Process&Manufacturing_Technologies"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_Handling&Storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_Handling&Storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Industrial_Process&Manufacturing_Technologies"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Natural_insulation_(wool_cotton_straw_etc.)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Natural_insulation_(wool_cotton_straw_etc.)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Material_based"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Refrigerators&Freezers
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Refrigerators&Freezers">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-28#Energy_Efficient_Appliances&Equipment"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

4. RDF script for Energy Conservation Practices Ontology

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Consevation_Practices">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Consevation_Practices">
<!--
//
// Classes
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Behavioural_practices
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Behavioural_practices">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Consevation_Practices"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_envelope_optimization
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_envelope_optimization">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Consevation_Practices"/>
</owl:Class>

```

```

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_Impact_from_system_optimization
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_Impact_from_system_optimization">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Performance"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_impact_from_Transportation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_impact_from_Transportation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Performance"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_impact_from_behavioural_practices
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Conservation_impact_from_behavioural_practices">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Performance"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#EVs
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#EVs">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Transportation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Efficient_use_of_energy_consuming_devices
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Efficient_use_of_energy_consuming_devices">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Behavioural_practices"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Performance
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Performance">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Practices"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Practices
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Practices"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_efficient_habits
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_efficient_habits">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Behavioural_practices"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Fuel_efficient_vehicles
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Fuel_efficient_vehicles">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Transportation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#HVAC_optimization
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#HVAC_optimization">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Lighting_optimization
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Lighting_optimization">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Public_transportation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Public_transportation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Transportation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Renewable_energy_systems_installation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Renewable_energy_systems_installation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Transportation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Transportation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_Conservation_Practices"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Water_conservation_measures
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Water_conservation_measures">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Building_systems_optimization"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_audits& assessments
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Energy_audits& assessments">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-29#Behavioural_practices"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

5. RDF script for Energy Generation Technologies and Sources

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Generation_Technologies_and_Sources">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Generation_Technologies_and_Sources"/>
<!--

```

```

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Data Properties
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#FuelType
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#FuelType"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Generation
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Generation"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#RES
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#RES"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Generation
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Generation"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#measurement"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#FuelType"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Generation"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#RES"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Generation"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#measurement
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#measurement">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#FuelType"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Generation"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#RES"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Generation"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!-- http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty -->
<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Biomass">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Coal
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Coal">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Electricity_Generation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Electricity_Generation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation">
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fuel_Type
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fuel_Type">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--

```

```

http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Gas
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Gas">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fuel_Type"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Geothermal_Power
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Geothermal_Power">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Heat_Generation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Heat_Generation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Hydro_Power
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Hydro_Power">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Liquid
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Liquid">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fuel_Type"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Measurement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Measurement">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Natural_Gas
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Natural_Gas">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Oil
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Oil">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fossil_Fuels"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Energy_Generation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Energy_Generation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Primary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Energy_Generation
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Energy_Generation">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solar_Power
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solar_Power">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solid
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solid">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Fuel_Type"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit_of_Measurement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit_of_Measurement">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Wind_Power
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Wind_Power">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Renewable_Energy_Sources"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#CHP_(Combined_Heat_and_Power_System)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#CHP_(Combined_Heat_and_Power_System)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Secondary_Energy_Generation"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Electricity_Generation:_kilowatt_hour_(kWh)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Electricity_Generation:_kilowatt_hour_(kWh)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit_of_Measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--

```

```

http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Liquid_Fuel:_Tons_oil_equivalent_(toe)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Liquid_Fuel:_Tons_oil_equivalent_(toe)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit_of_Measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solid_Fuel:_Cubic_meters_(m3)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Solid_Fuel:_Cubic_meters_(m3)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-17#Unit_of_Measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

6. RDF script for Energy Transmission and Distribution Systems Ontology

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Transmission_Systems">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Transmission_Systems">
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Data properties
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Commodity
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Commodity"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Length
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Length">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Commodity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Commodity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Commodity"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!-- http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty -->
<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity
-->

```

```

<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Current_Type
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Current_Type">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Electrical_Grid"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Electrical_Grid
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Electrical_Grid"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Energy_Commodity
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Energy_Commodity">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#High
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#High">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pressure"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Large
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Large">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Length
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Length">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Low
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Low">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pressure"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Medium
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Medium">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Operator">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline_System
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline_System">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Electrical_Grid"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pressure
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pressure">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Pipeline_System"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Puprose
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Puprose">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Rural
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Rural">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Small
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Small">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Capacity"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#StartDate">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--

```

```

http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Technologies">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Urban
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Urban">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Location"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage_Level
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage_Level">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Electrical_Grid"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Alternative_Current_(AC)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Alternative_Current_(AC)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Current_Type"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Direct_Current_(DC)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Direct_Current_(DC)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Current_Type"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#High_Voltage_(HV)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#High_Voltage_(HV)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage_Level"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Low_Voltage_(LV)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Low_Voltage_(LV)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage_Level"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Medium_Voltage_(MV)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Medium_Voltage_(MV)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-19#Voltage_Level"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

7. RDF script for Energy Consumption and Usage Patterns Ontology

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Consumption_and_Usage_Patterns">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Consumption_and_Usage_Patterns"/>
<!--
//
// Object Properties
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#hasNonRES
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#hasNonRES">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#usesEnergySource"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#hasRES
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#hasRES">
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#usesEnergySource"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#usesEnergySource
-->
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#usesEnergySource"/>
<!--
//
// Classes
//
//
//
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Bio_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Bio_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Renewable_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Coal_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Coal_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Fossil_Fuel_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Commercial

```



```

<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Usage_Pattern"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Natural_Gas_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Natural_Gas_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Fossil_Fuel_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Non_Renewable_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Non_Renewable_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Oil_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Oil_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Fossil_Fuel_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Property
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Property">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Consumption_Pattern"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Renewable_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Renewable_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Residential
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Residential">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Sector"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Sector
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Sector">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Consumption"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Solar_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Solar_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Renewable_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Unit_of_measurement
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Unit_of_measurement">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Usage_Type
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Usage_Type">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Consumption_Pattern"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Value
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Value">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Property"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Weekly
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Weekly">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Energy_Usage_Pattern"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Wind_Energy_Source
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Wind_Energy_Source">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Renewable_Energy_Source"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Electricity_Consumption:_kilowatt-hour_(kWh)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Electricity_Consumption:_kilowatt-hour_(kWh)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Unit_of_measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Liquid_Fuel_Consumption:_Tons_oil_equivalent_(toe)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Liquid_Fuel_Consumption:_Tons_oil_equivalent_(toe)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Unit_of_measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Solid_Fuel_Consumption:_Cubic_meters_(m3)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Solid_Fuel_Consumption:_Cubic_meters_(m3)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-25#Unit_of_measurement"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

8. RDF script for Energy Storage Systems and Technologies Ontology

```

<rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Storage_Systems_Technologies">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Energy_Storage_Systems_Technologies"/>
<!--
//
// Classes
//
//
//
-->
<!--
-->
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Ammonia_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Ammonia_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Capacitors
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Capacitors">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Electrostatic_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Combine_two_or_more_systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Combine_two_or_more_systems">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Hybrid_storage_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Compressed_air_energy_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Compressed_air_energy_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Mechanical_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Electrostatic_Energy_Storage_Systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Electrostatic_Energy_Storage_Systems">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Flow_batteries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Flow_batteries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Flywheels
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Flywheels">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Mechanical_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Hybrid_storage_system
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Hybrid_storage_system">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Hydrogen_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Hydrogen_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Latent_heat_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Latent_heat_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Lead_acid_batteries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Lead_acid_batteries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Lithium_ion_batteries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Lithium_ion_batteries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Mechanical_Energy_Storage_Systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Mechanical_Energy_Storage_Systems">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Methane_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Methane_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems">
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Phase_change_materials
-->

```

```

-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Phase_change_materials">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Pumped_hydroelectric_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Pumped_hydroelectric_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Mechanical_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Redox_batteries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Redox_batteries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Sensible_heat_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Sensible_heat_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Sodium_ion_batteries
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Sodium_ion_batteries">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Supercapacitors
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Supercapacitors">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#BESS_system"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermochemical_storage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermochemical_storage">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_Energy_Storage_Systems"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_energy_in_buildings_(e.g._hot_water_tanks)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Thermal_energy_in_buildings_(e.g._hot_water_tanks)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/untitled-ontology-26#Other_energy_storage_systems"/>
</owl:Class>
</rdf:RDF>

```

9. RDF script for Smart Devices Ontology

```

rdf:RDF xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Smart_Devices">
<owl:Ontology rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/dell/ontologies/2023/4/DATACELLAR/Smart_Devices"/>
<!--

//////////////////////////////////////
//
// Data properties
//
//////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERMeasurement
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERMeasurement">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERProperty"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERProperty
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERProperty">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERUnit"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!-- http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERUnit -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERUnit">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRMeasurement"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFFunction
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFFunction"/>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRMeasurement
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRMeasurement">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRProperty"/>
<rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>

```

```

<rdf:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRProperty
-->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRProperty">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRUnit"/>
<rdf:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<rdf:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!-- http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRUnit -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRUnit">
<owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<rdf:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#ERFunction"/>
<rdf:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#WRFunction"/>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>
<!-- http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty -->
<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#bottomDataProperty"/>
<!--

////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////

-->
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Calculate_energy_consumed_in_a_time_interval
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Calculate_energy_consumed_in_a_time_interval">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_ER
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_ER">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_WR">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_current_and_voltage
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_current_and_voltage">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_data
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_data">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_data_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_data_WR">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_weather-related_variables
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measure_weather-related_variables">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Function_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measurement_ER
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measurement_ER">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measurement_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Measurement_WR">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!-- http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power -->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_ER
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_ER">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_WR">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Send_data_for_billing_procedure
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Send_data_for_billing_procedure">
<rdf:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_ER"/>

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<owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Send_data_to_a_database
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Send_data_to_a_database">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Store_data
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Store_data">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Store_data_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Store_data_WR">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Property_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Active:_kilowatt_(kW)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Active:_kilowatt_(kW)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Ambient_noise:_decibels_(dB)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Ambient_noise:_decibels_(dB)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Ambient_temperature:_degrees_Celsius_(oC)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Ambient_temperature:_degrees_Celsius_(oC)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Apparent:_kilovolt_ampere_(kVA)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Apparent:_kilovolt_ampere_(kVA)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Current:_Ampere_(A)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Current:_Ampere_(A)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy:_kilowatt_hour_(kWh)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy:_kilowatt_hour_(kWh)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Energy_related_(smart_meter)"/>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power_factor:_w/o_dimension
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power_factor:_w/o_dimension">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Reactive:_kilovolt-ampere_reactive_(kVA_r)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Reactive:_kilovolt-ampere_reactive_(kVA_r)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Power"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Solar_irradiation:_Watt_per_square_meter_(Wm2)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Solar_irradiation:_Watt_per_square_meter_(Wm2)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Voltage:_Volt_(V)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Voltage:_Volt_(V)">
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_ER"/>
</owl:Class>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)
-->
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Weather_related_(sensor)"/>
<!--
http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Wind_speed:_meter_per_second_(ms-1)
-->

```

```
<owl:Class rdf:about="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Wind_speed:_meter_per_second_(ms-1)">  
<rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://www.co-ode.org/ontologies/ont.owl#Unit_of_measurement_WR"/>  
</owl:Class>  
</rdf:RDF>
```